

Contributions of African biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics to the One Health nexus

Josiah Ochieng Kuja¹, Cecilia Rumberia Waruhiu², Ichrak Hayah³, Hewan Demissie Degu⁴, Samira Ghoor⁵, Rae Marvin Smith⁶, Abdoallah Sharaf⁷, Samuel Paul Kagame⁸, Victor Ezebuoro⁹, Jacinta Abalaka^{10,11}, Asmaa M. Abushady^{12,13}, Victoria Omolola Adedeji¹⁴, Adedapo Olutola Adediji^{15,16}, Andrews Frimpong Adu¹⁷, Elvince Ager², Shakirat Oloruntoyin Ajenifujah-Solebo¹⁴, Genereux Akotenou¹⁸, Nabil Amor¹⁹, Brian Andika²⁰, Mai Barakat²¹, Komlan Batawila²², Zewdu Edea Bedada²³, Fatima Zahra Belharfi²⁴, Solomon Shiferaw Beyene²⁵, Carlos Bezuidenhout²⁶, Johannes Bezuidenhout²⁶, Kaoutar Bourak²⁷, Ezra Byakora²⁸, Nadia Carstens²⁹, Narjice Chafai³⁰, Kimberly Christine Coetzer³¹, Rim Drouzi^{3,24}, Achraf El Allali¹⁸, Benhamadi Mohammed El Amine²⁴, Owanate Elekima³², Assem Kadry Elsherif¹², Ojochenemi Aladi Enejoh¹⁴, Nidal Fahsi³³, Linda Fardeheb³⁴, Sarra Farjallah¹⁹, Nabil Fikraoui³³, Semir Bechir Suheil Gaouar²⁴, Yohannes Gedamu Gebre²³, Owunari Abraham Georgewill³⁵, Barrington Gesimba³⁶, Emna Ghouili¹⁸, Samuel Gicharu², Sotonye Leslie Gillis-Harry³², Andreas Gisel^{37,38}, Jesse Gitaka³⁹, Fatma Guerfali⁴⁰, Belei Wemboo Afiwa Halatoko⁴¹, Asmaa H. Hassan¹⁸, Sameh E. Hassanein^{12,42}, Mohamed Hijri³, Justin Eze Ideozu³², Franca Umasoye Igwe³², Dahaoui Ikram Ines²⁴, Faiza Ilias^{43,24}, Hakim Kaddour^{44,45}, Samira Kahia Tani³⁴, Agnetor Kakungu⁴⁶, Jonathan Kalami⁴⁷, Bernard N. Kanoi⁴⁸, Lewis Karani Mbabu⁴⁹, Sally Mueni Katee⁵⁰, Bekkar Kawther²⁴, Fredrick Kebaso⁵¹, Ahmed Marwane Kermouni Serradj³⁴, Rana S. Khalel²¹, Anubhab Khan^{52,53}, Racheal Kimani³⁹, Esther Kiragu⁴⁹, Natasha Kitchin⁵⁴, Dennis Manthi Kivuva²⁰, Komi Komi Koukoura⁵⁵, Eleojo Roseline Kwasi¹⁵, Kim Labuschagne⁵⁶, Michael Landi⁵⁷, Anja le Grange⁵⁸, Niguse Kelile Lema²³, Chidananda Lokesh³⁴, Brian Machua², Wenceslaus C Madu⁵⁹, Antoine Lusala Mafwila⁶⁰, Issaka Maman⁶¹, Mudzuli Mavhunga^{62,63}, Christina Meiring⁵⁸, George N. Michuki⁶⁴, Tabet Aoul Mohamed Wassim²⁴, Prudent Sankwetea Mokgokong²⁶, Morad M. Mokhtar⁶⁵, Roba Hamed Mostafa²¹, Ismail Mouhrach³³, Ahmed Moustafa²¹, Benard Mugisha⁶⁶, Zahra Mungloo-Dilmohamud⁶⁷, Shane Murray⁵⁸, Monica Mwale⁶⁸, Peter Nthiga Mwangi², Martin Naicker²⁹, Olivier Nicky⁶⁹, Valentine Otang Ntui³, Helen Nigussie⁷⁰, William Nyakundi²⁰, Ebele Obichi⁹, David Obute², Blessing Adanta Odogwu³⁵, Joel Ogwang²⁸, Johnpaul Okorochoa⁵⁹, Okiemute Ajiroghene Okpalefe¹⁴, Monday Iko-Ojo Okpanachi¹⁰, Oluwaseyi Samuel Olanrewaju²⁶, Adetutu Excellence Olumeh¹⁵, Taiwo Crossby Omotoriogun^{71,10}, Laura Nyasita Ondari⁵⁷, Genevive Chimezie Osuji⁷², Houcemeddine Othman^{73,74}, Amged Ouf^{21,75}, Jacktone Oyoo⁷⁶, Jacques Potgieter⁵⁴, Pritika Ramharack^{77,78}, Zineb Rchiad²⁷, Shaimaa Reda¹², Zahra Salah²⁴, Samson Pandam Salifu⁴⁷, Ntji Shabangu⁷⁹, Iyeopu Minakiri Siminialayi³⁵, Francois Smit⁸⁰, Hiroaki Taniguchi^{3,81}, Talatu Tende¹⁰, Kassahun Tesfaye^{23,82}, Chigoziem Ruth Torty⁸³, Ogbuagu Ugorji Udensi⁸⁴, Erich van Wyk⁵⁶, Sammy Wambua⁵³, Victoria Wavinya Wambua²⁰, Elsabet Wessels⁸⁰, Michaela-Anne White⁸⁰, Bret Wurdeman⁷⁹, Firas Zemzem^{85,86}, Renate Dorothea Zipfel⁶⁹, Yedomon Ange Bovys Zoclanclounon⁸⁷, Bouabid Badaoui^{88,89*}, Craig John Kinnear^{5*}, Julian Onyewuonyeoma Osuji^{35,9*}, ThankGod Echezona Ebenezer^{90*}, Anne WT Muigai^{91,90*}

*Corresponding authors: bouabidbadaoui@gmail.com, craig.kinnear2@mrc.ac.za, julian.osuji@uniport.edu.ng, thankgod1980@yahoo.co.uk, awmuigai@yahoo.co.uk

¹Washington State University, Global Health, Nairobi, Kenya, ²F&S Scientific, Nairobi, Kenya, ³African Genome Center (AGC), University Mohammed VI Polytechnic (UM6P), Ben Guerir, Morocco, ⁴Hawassa University, College of Agriculture, School of Plant and Horticulture Sciences, Hawassa, Ethiopia, ⁵Genomics Platform, South African Medical Research Council (SAMRC), Cape Town, South Africa, ⁶Department of Life and Consumer Sciences, University of South Africa, Roodepoort, South Africa, ⁷SequAna Core Facility, Department of Biology, University of Konstanz, Konstanz, Germany, ⁸Ghent University, Ghent, Belgium, ⁹South-South Zonal Centre of Excellence, University of Port Harcourt, Choba, Nigeria, ¹⁰A.P. Leventis Ornithological Research Institute (APLORI), Jos, Nigeria, ¹¹University of Jos, Jos, Nigeria, ¹²Biotechnology School, Nile University, Giza, Egypt, ¹³Department of Genetics, Faculty of Agriculture, Ain Shams University, Cairo, Egypt, ¹⁴National Biotechnology Research & Development Agency (NBRDA), Abuja, FCT, Nigeria, ¹⁵Inqaba Biotec West Africa, Ibadan, Nigeria, ¹⁶Pan African University Life and Earth Sciences Institute, Ibadan, Nigeria, ¹⁷Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Kumasi, Ghana, ¹⁸Bioinformatics Laboratory, College of Computing, University Mohammed VI Polytechnic (UM6P), Ben Guerir, Morocco, ¹⁹University of Tunis El Manar, Tunis, Tunisia, ²⁰Inqaba Biotec East Africa Ltd., Nairobi, Kenya, ²¹The American University in Cairo, New Cairo, Egypt, ²²Laboratory of Botany and Plant Ecology (LBEV), Faculty of Sciences, University of Lomé, Lomé, Togo, ²³Bio and Emerging Technology Institute (BETin), Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, ²⁴Applied genetics in agriculture, ecology and public health laboratory, University of Tlemcen, Tlemcen, Algeria, ²⁵College of Agriculture, Hawassa University, Hawassa, Ethiopia, ²⁶Unit for Environmental Sciences and Management, North-West University, Potchefstroom, South Africa, ²⁷Biosciences CoreLab, University Mohammed VI Polytechnic (UM6P), Ben Guerir, Morocco, ²⁸National Animal Genetic Resources Centre and Data Bank (NAGRC&DB), Entebbe, Uganda, ²⁹Genomics Platform, South African Medical Research Council (SAMRC), Capetown, South Africa, ³⁰Agronomic and Veterinary Institute Hassan II (IAV), Rabat, Morocco, ³¹Division of Molecular Biology and Human Genetics, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Stellenbosch University, Cape Town, South Africa, ³²MyAfroDNA, Port Harcourt, Nigeria, ³³BioSciences CoreLab, University Mohammed VI Polytechnic (UM6P), Ben Guerir, Morocco, ³⁴Genetical, Oran, Algeria, ³⁵University of Port Harcourt (UniPort), Choba, Nigeria, ³⁶Shomoro technologies, Nairobi, Kenya, ³⁷International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Ibadan, Nigeria, ³⁸Institute for Biomedical Technologies (CNR-ITB), Bari, Italy, ³⁹Mount Kenya University, Thika, Kenya, ⁴⁰Institut Pasteur de Tunis, Tunis, Tunisia, ⁴¹National Institute of Hygiene (INH), Lomé, Togo, ⁴²Agricultural Genetic Engineering Research Institute (AGERI), Agriculture Research Center (ARC), Giza, Egypt, ⁴³Applied hydrology and Environment Laboratory, Faculty of sciences and Technology, University of Ain Temouchent, Ain Temouchent, Algeria, ⁴⁴2- faculté des sciences et technologie, Université Aïn Temouchent, Ain Temouchent, Algeria, ⁴⁵1-École nationale supérieure des sciences géodésiques et des techniques spatiales (ENSGTS), Arzew, ⁴⁶KEMRI-Wellcome Trust, Kilifi, Kenya, ⁴⁷Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology (KNUST), Kumasi, Ghana, ⁴⁸Mount Kenya University (MKU), Thika, Kenya, ⁴⁹Change Biotec Limited, Nairobi, Kenya, ⁵⁰International Livestock Research Institute (ILRI), Nairobi, Kenya, ⁵¹Kenyatta University, Nairobi, Kenya, ⁵²Centre for Ecological Sciences, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore, India, ⁵³Pwani University, Kilifi, Kenya, ⁵⁴Separations, Johannesburg, South Africa, ⁵⁵Laboratory of Biomedical Sciences, Food and Environmental Health (LaSBASE), University of Lomé, Lomé, Togo, ⁵⁶Science Collections, Foundational Biodiversity Science, South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI), Pretoria, South Africa, ⁵⁷International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Nairobi, Kenya, ⁵⁸DIPLOMICS, Cape Town, South Africa, ⁵⁹Claretian University of Nigeria, Nekede, Nigeria, ⁶⁰University of Kinshasa, Kinshasa, DR Congo, ⁶¹Laboratory of Virology and Molecular Biology, National Institute of Hygiene (INH), Lomé, Togo, ⁶²Biodiversity Biobanks South Africa (BBSA), Pretoria, South Africa, ⁶³South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI), Pretoria, South Africa, ⁶⁴The Africa Genomics Center and Consultancy, Nairobi, Kenya, ⁶⁵College of Chemical Sciences and Engineering

(CCSE), Chemical and Biochemical Sciences (CBS), Univeristy Mohammed VI Polytechnic (UM6P), Benguerir, Morocco, ⁶⁶Bishop Stuart University, Mbarara, Uganda, ⁶⁷University of Mauritius, Reduit, Mauritius, ⁶⁸Zoological Research, Foundational Biodiversity Science, South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI), Pretoria, South Africa, ⁶⁹University of Pretoria, Pretoria, South Africa, ⁷⁰Addis Ababa University, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, ⁷¹Elizade University, Ilara-Mokin, Nigeria, ⁷²Department of Linguistics and Communication Studies, University of Calabar, Calabar, Nigeria, ⁷³Laboratory of Cytogenetics, Molecular Genetics and Reproductive Biology (LR03SP02), Farhat Hached University Hospital, University of Sousse, Sousse, Tunisia, ⁷⁴Sydney Brenner Institute for Molecular Bioscience, University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, South Africa, ⁷⁵Generations Genetics Labs, Cairo, Egypt, ⁷⁶International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology (ICIPE), Nairobi, Kenya, ⁷⁷Centre for Tuberculosis Research, South African Medical Research Council (SAMRC), Cape Town, South Africa, ⁷⁸Division of Molecular Biology and Human Genetics, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Stellenbosch University, Stellenbosch, South Africa, ⁷⁹MGI-Tech, Shenzhen, China, ⁸⁰Cengen (Pty) Ltd, Worcester, South Africa, ⁸¹Department of Experimental Embryology, Institute of Genetics and Animal Biotechnology of the Polish Academy of Sciences, Jastrzębiec, Poland, ⁸²College of Natural and Computational Sciences, Addis Ababa University, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, ⁸³Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria, ⁸⁴University of Calabar, Calabar, Nigeria, ⁸⁵Higher Institute of Biotechnology of Monastir, University of Monastir, Monastir, Tunisia, ⁸⁶Laboratory of Human Cytogenetics, Molecular Genetics and Reproductive Biology, Farhat Hached University Hospital, University of Sousse, Sousse, Tunisia, ⁸⁷Rothamsted Research, Harpenden, United Kingdom, ⁸⁸Faculty of Sciences, Mohammed V University in Rabat (UM5R), Rabat, Morocco, ⁸⁹African Sustainable Agriculture Research Institute, University Mohammed VI Polytechnic (UM6P), Laâyoune, Morocco, ⁹⁰African BioGenome Project (AfricaBP), Juja, Kenya, ⁹¹National Defence University-Kenya, Nakuru, Kenya

Abstract

Africa's biodiversity sustains ecosystems, supporting humans, animals, plants, and the environment. It is, however, increasingly facing pressure, justifying the need for an integrated One Health approach that addresses human, animal, plants, and environmental health holistically. Additionally, the role of genomics and bioinformatics in One Health, especially in the context of food security, agriculture, environment and biodiversity conservation, has been underutilized. The African BioGenome Project (AfricaBP) has, since 2022, been raising awareness on the importance of genomics and bioinformatics in biodiversity conservation, preservation, and sustainable use and innovations. Through its AfricaBP Open Institute, the project promotes knowledge sharing and scientific entrepreneurship, and strengthens data sovereignty. In 2025 the AfricaBP Open Institute held 45 workshops across 12 African countries, training 545 African researchers in various skills, including genome sequencing, bioinformatics analysis, molecular biology, sample collection, biobanking, ethical, legal and social aspects of genetic resources, and attracted 4980 registered participants across 75 countries worldwide. Here, we provide a status update on One Health approaches in Africa, scanning various implementation models adopted at national, regional, and continental levels. We also underscore the importance of implementing African One Health strategies using biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics as tools. We propose a set of recommendations such as establishing more national One Health strategic plans and networks funded and governed through national and local funding mechanisms to focus on actualising national and regional priorities, establishing integrated Pan-African One Health Framework for Biodiversity Genomics and Bioinformatics to drive sustainable conservation and food security, better connect socio-economics and policy issues. Finally, we provide insights into how biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics could be leveraged to inform One Health policies through quantitative and qualitative sequence data and information.

Keywords: Africa, biodiversity, agriculture, genomics, bioinformatics, workshops, one health, awareness, capacity strengthening, networks, one health strategic plans

Background

Biodiversity is central to One Health, influencing both the spillover of zoonotic diseases and the transmission of pathogens from humans to animals (anthroponosis), as witnessed during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic (Alimi & Wabacha, 2023; Anjorin et al., 2021). The One Health High-Level Expert Panel (OHHLEP) (One Health High-Level Expert Panel (OHHLEP) et al., 2022), the scientific advisory body to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH), the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP), and the World Health Organization (WHO) (WHO, 2025), defines One Health as an integrated, unifying approach that aims to sustainably balance and optimise the health of people, animals, and ecosystems, recognising that the health of humans, domestic and wild animals, plants, and the wider environments and ecosystems are closely linked and interdependent (One Health High-Level Expert Panel (OHHLEP) et al., 2022). To implement this vision, OHHLEP supports partners and member states in developing strategies and plans, including the Joint Plan of Action for One Health (2022–2026), the main framework for coordinating cross-sectoral collaboration between FAO, WOAH, UNEP, and WHO (One Health High-Level Expert Panel (OHHLEP) et al., 2022).

Africa's rich biodiversity (Bezeng et al., 2025) is deeply entrenched in human cultures, traditions, and the socio-economic fabric (da Cunha, 2017; Rozzi, 2018). It sustains healthy ecosystems which support the health of its populations, the environment, and industry (Archer et al., 2021; Fajinmi et al., 2025; Sintayehu, 2018). Across the continent, biodiversity hotspots face mounting pressures, stressing the need for an integrated One Health approach that strengthens the health of biodiversity and ensures the survival of African indigenous and endemic species (Ngongolo & Kyando, 2025; Winkler et al., 2025). While One Health is gradually gaining traction in Africa (Fasina et al., 2022), only 16 of 55 African Union Member States have established National One Health Strategic Plans (NOHSPs) (see Table 1 and One Health Commission, 2025). Implementation is supported through existing or newly established One Health Networks (OHNs), such as, the African One Health University Network (Amer et al., 2025), Africa One REACH (Bonfoh et al., 2024; Dindé et al., 2025), and other regional platforms (Fokou et al., 2025; Rwego et al., 2016).

An OHN is defined as a collaboration between two or more institutions represented by at least two of the three One Health sectors: human health, animal health, and ecosystem or environmental health (Mwatondo et al., 2023). Of the 184 OHNs identified globally in 2023, 42% (78) operate in Africa, yet only 10% (8) are headquartered on the continent (Mwatondo et al., 2023), reflecting ongoing disparities and inequalities in global One Health leadership and decision-making (Elnaiem et al., 2023). Research

activity and funding remain heavily focused on emerging infections, zoonoses, and antimicrobial resistance (AMR) (Gashema et al., 2025; Mwatondo et al., 2023; Wilhelm et al., 2025), while fewer initiatives address food safety, crop and livestock health, livelihoods, biodiversity loss, wider ecosystem dynamics (Omuse et al., 2025) or genetic diversity of plants, animals, and microbes.

Genomics and bioinformatics are increasingly recognised as catalytic drivers of One Health advancement (Scarpa & Casu, 2024; Vallejo-Espín et al., 2025). These approaches deepen understanding of pathogen evolution, human genetic variation, transmission pathways, and host-pathogen interactions across species and environments (Scarpa & Casu, 2024), while also enabling real-time ecological assessments (Urban et al., 2023). However, a Web of Science search conducted on 14 November 2025 identified 576 One Health publications relating to Africa over the past 25 years, of which 205 (36%) mentioned agriculture and 34 (6%) mentioned biodiversity; only one mentioned genomics or bioinformatics. The contributions of genomics and bioinformatics to disease surveillance and human health is well demonstrated (Calcino et al., 2024; Moir et al., 2025), yet applications to biodiversity monitoring, ecosystem resilience, and the broader One Health interface remain underdeveloped in tropical regions, including Africa (Calcino et al., 2024).

Despite growing recognition of human health and pathogen dynamics within the One Health approach in Africa (Amer et al., 2025), limited attention has been given to the broader roles of plants, animals, fungi, protists, and other eukaryotes in maintaining ecosystem balance and influencing disease emergence and transmission. Since 2022, the African BioGenome Project (AfricaBP) (<https://africanbiogenome.org>) has focused on raising awareness of biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics. AfricaBP is the first continental initiative to aim to sequence the genomes of African endemic species, to improve food systems, conserve biodiversity, and ensure equitable data sharing (Ebenezer et al., 2022). Through its Open Institute, AfricaBP promotes grassroots knowledge sharing, strengthens data sovereignty, promotes scientific entrepreneurship, and aims to develop curricula, infrastructure, and technologies (Sharaf et al., 2023). Building on workshops from 2022-2024 (Hayah et al., 2025; Sharaf et al., 2023, 2024). In 2025 the AfricaBP Open Institute held 45 workshops across 12 African countries, training 545 African researchers in genome sequencing, bioinformatics analysis, molecular biology, sample collection, biobanking, and ethical, legal, and social aspects of genetic resource use, while attracting 4,980 participants from 75 countries.

Building on the outcomes of the 2025 workshops, this paper also aims to: 1) delineate insights into the significance of biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics on the African One Health as well as advance our understanding and knowledge in this area, 2) predict the health, food security, and conservation impact of biodiversity genomics and

bioinformatics knowledge systems on African One Health strategies and offer recommendations using Kenya as a case study, 3) discuss progress of the AfricaBP workshops since 2022 through comparative trend analysis, 4) provide current understanding on the applications of biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics to One Health strategies across Africa, 5) summarise the course contents of the AfricaBP Open Institute Regional Workshops in 2025, 6) discuss the progress of the AfricaBP partnering Fellowships, 7) discuss lessons learned from the third edition of the AfricaBP Open Institute regional workshops in 2025.

The Landscape of African National One Health Strategic Plans (NOHSPs): African biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics for One Health

There are three mechanisms by which African countries operationalise One Health, these include One Health initiatives, OHNs, and/or NOHSPs. Among these, the NOHSPs allow countries to anchor One Health onto their national agenda. We have previously described OHNs and NOHSPs. One Health (OH) initiatives are collaborative efforts that promote the interconnectedness of human, animal, and environmental health to prevent and control diseases and other health threats, characterized by utilizing cross-sectoral or multi-sectoral aspects in communication, collaboration, coordination or capacity building on issues like pandemic preparedness, disease surveillance, and the impact of climate change (Auplish et al., 2024). The implementation of One Health initiatives, OHNs, and NOHSPs involve collaborations with diverse stakeholders at the local, national, regional, and global levels (Omuse et al., 2025). As of 2020 and 2023, there were approximately 300 One Health initiatives (Fasina et al., 2021; Fasina & Fasanmi, 2020) and 78 OHNs (Mwatondo et al., 2023) across Africa, respectively. At the national, regional, and continental levels, there are about 16 NOHSPs (One Health Commission, 2025; Wilhelm et al., 2025) that drive actionable insights on One Health (see Table 1).

Many African countries have gradually institutionalized the One Health approach through national strategic action plans as summarized in Table 1, but human and animal health dominate nearly all these plans. Only a few African countries have established a comprehensive One Health strategy that inclusively addresses biodiversity and agricultural interests, especially on genetic diversity (see Table 1 and (One Health Commission, 2025; Wilhelm et al., 2025) for details on NOHPs across Africa). Some African countries such as Namibia, Cameroon, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Burkina Faso, Egypt, Ethiopia, Kenya, Guinea, Liberia, Sierra Leone, Nigeria, Rwanda, Tanzania, South Sudan, Uganda, and Zambia have developed and published formal NOHPs. These strategies are each shaped by local epidemiological priorities and

governance structures (See Table 1). Some national and regional efforts are further supported by the quadripartite organizations (FAO, UNEP, WHO and WOA) One Health Joint Plan of Action (2022-2026), which provides continental guidance for integrated policy implementation (One Health Joint Plan of Action (2022–2026), 2022).

Moreover, the African Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (Africa CDC) and Africa Union - Inter-Africa Bureau for Animal Resources (AU-IBAR) developed a robust framework to guide, especially national public health institutions, in implementing One Health and aims to strengthen multisectoral coordination, enhance surveillance and data sharing system, improve early detection and response, climate change as well as build capacity and promote joint research initiatives (Africa CDC, 2025a, 2025b).

NOHSPs in some African countries, particularly Kenya, Uganda, Ethiopia, Tanzania, and Zambia, link biodiversity, ecosystem integrity, and agricultural sustainability to zoonotic risk reduction and food security (Table 1) (Wilhelm et al., 2025). For instance, Uganda's plan supports human, biodiversity, food and feed, and environmental health as a determinant of the evolution and spread of zoonotic diseases (Table 1) (Buregyeya et al., 2020), while Kenya's strategy directly connects agricultural practices to disease surveillance and public health (Table 1) (Munyua et al., 2019). Similarly, Zambia integrates health of human, animal and environment within their climate adaptation and agricultural productivity frameworks, framing ecosystem health as a resilient strategy against both epidemics and food safety (Table 1).

By contrast, Nigeria's One Health strategy emphasises agricultural productivity, food safety and food security as central objectives, while environmental and biodiversity dimensions are articulated less explicitly (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2019) than in several East African NOHSPs (Table 1) (Lucero-Prisno III et al., 2023; Wilhelm et al., 2025). In North Africa, we could not find stand-alone One Health strategies for Morocco, Tunisia, and Algeria in the public domain (Table 1), but they exhibit growing conceptual alignment with One Health through environmental health, food safety, and climate adaptation policies (Zyoud & Zyoud, 2025). These frameworks are oriented more towards environmental determinants of ecosystem health and sustainability (Shadomy et al., 2025), rather than the operational multisectoral models adopted in East Africa (Table 1) (Kitua et al., 2019).

NOHSPs in Nigeria, the Democratic Republic of Congo, Kenya, Guinea, Zambia, and South Sudan prioritize zoonotic diseases, environmental health, and antimicrobial resistance (AMR), while Uganda adds biosecurity to the equation (Table 1). Rwanda, Egypt, Uganda, and Cameroon broadly integrate plant health with human and animal health, while Cameroon's 2024-2028 One Health plan promotes surveillance across plant, animal, and environmental systems (Table 1). Tanzania's 2022-2027 plan

incorporates wildlife and environmental health but restricts surveillance to classical epidemiology (Table 1). Similarly, Liberia and Sierra Leone assign roles to environmental and wildlife agencies, yet remain primarily zoonosis-centered. Mauritius has several strategic plans related to One Health such as the Health Sector Strategic Plan 2020-2024 (Republic of Mauritius, 2020) and National Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance 2024-2028 (Republic of Mauritius, 2024), though none of these comprehensively addresses the One Health nexus. South Africa also has several strategic plans related to One Health but not a unified NOHSP as highlighted in Table 1, and they include, amongst others, the South African Antimicrobial Resistance National Strategy Framework 2017-2024 (Republic of South Africa, 2017) and the Integrated Disease Surveillance and Response Framework (Ng'etich et al., 2021; World Health Organisation, 2024)

Despite Africa's extraordinary biodiversity and high potential for zoonotic emergence, NOHSPs remain reactive rather than preventive (Otu et al., 2021). Surveillance systems are confined to pathogen and outbreak-based models (Milazzo et al., 2025). These strategies do not include biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics as well as molecular biology for ecosystem monitoring, leveraging genomic and molecular surveillance as instruments for epidemic control with limited emphasis on biodiversity and ecosystem monitoring (Table 1) (Gashema et al., 2025). Collaboration and capacity building are well-articulated, yet refer to governance, training, and infrastructure rather than molecular expertise in the genomics era (Table 1) (Wilhelm et al., 2025). Burkina Faso, for instance, has focused its capacity-building efforts on veterinary professionals in infection control, improving laboratories infrastructures and prioritizing the surveillance of zoonotic diseases (FAO, 2019). Operational and policy coordination, capacity -building and -strengthening, communications and outreach, resourcing, research and innovation, reporting, monitoring and evaluation, are common themes that are essential in delivering and implementing NOHSPs across most African countries (see relevant NOHSPs in Table 1 for more details).

African countries have made substantial progress in establishing One Health (OH) strategic plans, but operational and structural challenges persist across the continent. In Guinea, regional OH platforms remain under-resourced and functionally weak, with 41% national performance score. Major gaps at the national level include limited resource and regional disparities in transportation and digital data-sharing systems (Emile Faya Bongono et al., 2025; Emile F. Bongono et al., 2025). Post-Ebola evaluations from Guinea, Liberia, and Sierra Leone further highlight difficulties in sustaining multisectoral collaboration, harmonizing policies, and institutionalizing long-term outbreak-preparedness at the national level (Agbo et al., 2019). In Tanzania, despite advancement in national OH strategic plans and strong political anchorage, challenges

persist in creating awareness, limited funding, and inadequate monitoring and evaluation systems (Vianney et al., 2024). This scenario is the same in Cameroon (Fossouo & Mouliom, 2024), Nigeria (Lucero-Prisno III et al., 2023), and most developing nations (Yopa et al., 2023). Rwanda demonstrates stronger governance, with OH strategic plan anchored at high political levels and integrated into high level academic curriculum, yet still faces under representation and inconsistent dissemination across institutions. Most of the institutional OH programs are donor-dependent and not community-based operations (Shyaka et al., 2024). Collectively, successful implementation or execution of African OH strategic plans are hindered by the fragmented structural governance from the national to regional levels and high level political will is also weakened by donor-dependency or limited will for national governments to co-fund One Health initiatives, networks and strategic plans (Otu et al., 2021). For example, several of the NOHSPs in Table 1 were enabled through donor support rather than outright national funding. However, several African countries have recorded successful implementation of One Health strategies (Otu et al., 2021).

Table 1: Some of the One Health Strategic Plans across Africa

S/N	Level	Organisations and/or Countries	Strategy	Example priority areas	Reference
1	Continental	Africa Center for Disease Control (Africa CDC) and the African Union – Inter-African Bureau for Animal Resources (AU-IBAR)	Climate Change & Health Strategic Framework (2025–2029) Zoonotic Disease Prevention & Control Strategy (2025–2030)	Health impacts of Climate Change Zoonotic disease, food safety, and climate change	(Africa CDC, 2025a) (Africa CDC, 2025b)
2	Regional	Economic Community of West African States West African Health Organization	ECOWAS One Health Strategy (2025–2029) and Governance Manual	Zoonotic disease surveillance, inter-sectoral collaboration, regional surveillance	(Sogbossi et al., 2025)
3	Regional	East African Community	Draft EAC Regional One Health Strategy 2022 - 2027	Infectious diseases and other events of public health concern	(The East African Community (EAC), 2022)
4	National	Republic of Namibia Namibian government and Africa CDC for Strategy 2024–2028	Tripartite One Health National Strategy 2024–2028 Namibia National Action Plan for Health Security (2021-2025)	Zoonotic, vector-borne, and tropical diseases, antimicrobial resistance, and environment	(Africa CDC, 2024; World Health Organization, Regional Office for Africa (WHO AFRO), 2021)
5	National	Burkina Faso	Burkina Faso National One Health Platform	Zoonotic diseases such as rabies and anthrax	(FAO, 2019; Goryoka et al., 2021; Nana et al., 2022; Savadogo et

S/N	Level	Organisations and/or Countries	Strategy	Example priority areas	Reference
					al., 2025)
6	National	Cameroon	Cameroon One Health Action Plan 2024 - 2028 National One Health Strategy	Prevention, preparedness, and response to public health events, (re)-emerging diseases and threats, surveillance, investigations and response systems for environment, plant, animal, and human health	(Cameroon One Health Platform, 2024; Pouokam et al., 2017)
7	National	Democratic Republic of the Congo	DRC National One Health Strategic Plan 2022-2027	Animal health (wild and domestic), human and environmental, zoonotic diseases, antimicrobial resistance, food safety and security	(Republic Democratic du Congo, 2022)
8	National	Egypt	Egypt National One Health Operational Plan 2024-2027 Egypt National Strategic Framework for OH 2023-2027	Zoonotic and vector-borne diseases, food and water safety, antimicrobial resistance, effective response to health threats facing humans, animals, plants, and the environment	(Egyptian Environmental Affairs Agency, 2023; Ministry of Health and Population, Arab Republic of Egypt, 2022)
9	National	Ethiopia	National One Health Five-Year Strategic Plan (2025/26-2029/30)	Zoonotic diseases, antimicrobial resistance, food safety, and environmental risks	(Ethiopian Public Health Institute (EPHI), 2025)

S/N	Level	Organisations and/or Countries	Strategy	Example priority areas	Reference
10	National	Kenya	One Health Strategic Plan for the Prevention and Control of Zoonotic Diseases in Kenya (2021-2025) National Strategic Plan for OH in Kenya (2012-2017)	Zoonotic diseases in humans and animals, infectious diseases	(Zoonotic Disease Unit, 2012, 2021)
11	National	Guinea	One Health Strategic Plan for Guinea (2019-2023)	Human, animal, and public health, zoonotic diseases, livestock biosafety, ecosystem health and climate-related health	(Republique de Guinee, 2018)
12	National	Liberia	National One Health Strategic Plan – September 2018 Liberia National One Health Platform	Human health, animal health, wildlife and biodiversity, zoonotic diseases, environmental health, food safety, disaster preparedness and response, and antimicrobial resistance	(Liberia One Health Platform, 2018)
13	National	Sierra Leone	National One Health Platform 2018	Zoonotic and infectious diseases, surveillance, public health, antimicrobial resistance	(Republic of Sierra Leone, 2018)
14	National	Nigeria	One Health Strategic Plan 2019-2023	Zoonotic and infectious diseases, food safety and security, improve livelihoods, public and	(Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2019)

S/N	Level	Organisations and/or Countries	Strategy	Example priority areas	Reference
				animal health	
15	National	Rwanda	One Health Strategic Plan 2021 - 2026	Human, animals (domestic, wildlife) and environment. management of (re)-emerging infectious such as plant, zoonotic, vector-borne, and food-borne diseases, antimicrobial resistance and other public health issues	(Republic of Rwanda, 2021)
16	National	Tanzania	Tanzania National One Health Strategic Plan (2022–2027)	Zoonotic disease outbreaks related to human, animal (wildlife and livestock) and environmental health, biorisk management, antimicrobial resistance, food safety and security, (re)-emerging health issues, non- communicable diseases and other events of public health concern	(The United Republic of Tanzania Prime Minister’s Office, 2022)
17	National	South Sudan	South Sudan National Action Plan for Health Security (NAPHS) 2020-2024 One Health Strategic Plan and the 2nd National Action Plan for	Food safety, biosafety and biosecurity, human-animal interface, health security, zoonotic disease, antimicrobial resistance	(Republic of South Sudan, 2020; WHO African Region, 2024; World Health Organization (WHO), 2025)

S/N	Level	Organisations and/or Countries	Strategy	Example priority areas	Reference
			Health Security (2025-2030)		
18	National	Uganda	Uganda One Health Strategic Plan 2018 - 2022	Zoonotic disease, antimicrobial resistance, and biosecurity	(Republic of Uganda, 2018)
19	National	Zambia	National One Health Strategic Plan 2022 - 2026	Public health, zoonotic disease, optimise health of human, animal, and environment	(Republic of Zambia, 2022)

How African national biodiversity genomics projects could help contribute to components of national One Health Strategic Plans: A Kenya case study

Kenya's National One Health Strategic Plan recognises the interconnectedness between human, animal and environmental health, and implements an integrated One Health approach towards the control and prevention of the spread of diseases in Kenya (see Table 1). The Kenyan NOHSP acknowledges that human activities have a huge impact on the environment, resulting in environmental degradation, biodiversity loss and unsustainable agricultural activities, therefore exposing the public to health risks that directly affect livelihoods and Kenya's development (Zoonotic Disease Unit, 2012, 2021).

However, a One Health approach in Kenya could consider not only disease surveillance and prevention of spread of zoonotic diseases, but also the development and support of resilient ecosystems that support healthy people, plants and animals, both domestic and wildlife. Using the proposed 100 Kenyan national biodiversity genomics project, we carried out a *lightweight, scoping-level* One Health analysis involving its *selected* proposed species to sequence (84), already sequence Kenyan genomes (68), *potential* stakeholders, actual processes, and sectors impacted in a genomics-driven One Health value chain (see Figure 1, 2, 3, 4 and Text Box 1). We limited our analysis to non-biological interactions in the One Health network to produce a prototype framework for a comprehensive One Health analysis framework with biological depth (see conclusion, recommendation, and next step section). Using a multi-sectoral scoping approach, we identified and mapped the central role of Kenya's One Health players relevant to humans, pathogens, agriculture, and biodiversity as well as biodiversity genomics informed insights on how stakeholders could better coordinate in the One Health framework. For the non-human and non-pathogen players, the roles are likely to be overlooked because the institutional mandates may be defined primarily around environmental conservation rather than directly on One Health. However, we show that non-human health institutions have a key role to play in One Health (Figure 2), highlighting opportunities that could be leveraged in the implementation of the One Health strategy within the Kenya

The proposed 100 Kenyan National Biodiversity Genomics Project seeks to sequence 100 indigenous or endemic Kenyan species, including microbial communities across Kenya's territorial, freshwater and marine ecosystems and will generate crucial biodata that could be used to operationalise Kenya's National One Health Strategic Plan. The proposed project could create reference genomic libraries and baselines for Kenya's biodiversity across taxonomic groups, carefully selected, to provide data that supports decision making across several sectors from conservation to economy (Figure 1, 3 and

4) as well as being of relevance to several potential stakeholders from the National Museum of Kenya to the State Department for Trade (Figure 2). Data generated may be relevant in documenting ongoing effects of climate change on Kenya's flora, fauna and humans through process versus species interactions, and stakeholders versus process interactions (Figure 4). For example, application of such sequenced data in disease surveillance could serve as an early warning system for zoonotic related pathogens and other vectors that interphase between wildlife, livestock, humans and the environment, and more importantly, for understanding the genetic basis of crop and plant resistance to adverse environmental conditions (Figure 1, 2 and 4).

Recognising the threat posed by Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) globally, Kenya has developed a joint National Policy on the Prevention and Containment of Antimicrobial Resistance under the One Health Approach (Mukoko et al., 2025). The National Action Plan on AMR (NAR-AMR) integrates human and animal health, agriculture, fisheries and environmental sectors. However, to be effective, it requires Monitoring and Evaluation (M&E), and the availabilities of genomic data across a wide range of indigenous and endemic Kenya species provides the opportunities for such M&E, considering that the M&E component of One Health has been weak in most low and middle income countries (Wesangula et al., 2020; Willemsen et al., 2022). For example, genome assembly levels shows weak associations with International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) status and endemism variable, implying low frequencies or coverage of available genome assemblies (scaffold, contig, chromosome, or complete genome levels) for species (introduced, native or endemic) benefitting from conservation significance in Kenya (Figure 3). This is supported by previous investigations and a report (Matheson & McGaughan, 2022; McLaughlin et al., 2025) which suggests that several species on the IUCN red list are missing genetic information to inform conservation strategies.

Finally, the 100 Kenyan National Biodiversity Genomics Project will enhance food security directly by contributing critical information that would be used in crop and animal improvement programmes (Figure 1 and 4). Application of genomics and bioinformatics to crops and livestock, would identify important genes, including those with drought tolerance, disease resistance and those that enhance the bioavailability and nutrition of plants. Genomic data could act as an accelerator for the production of fast-growing, climate-friendly crops and livestock that would ensure the provision of sustainable food and crops for the Kenyan populace.

Figure 1: The proposed Kenyan national biodiversity genomics project will have profound effects across multiple sectors within the One Health framework: The diagram shows a heatmap that illustrates associations between 71 selected Kenyan biodiversity species (sequenced and unsequenced; introduced, native and endemic) and Kenyan One Health sectors. The Y-axis represents the selected species shown on the heatmap One Health analysis. The X-axis represents sectors within the One Health framework (see Text Box 1 for additional information). Hierarchical clustering was applied to identify patterns of co-occurrence and sectoral alignment between sectors and identified species. Association strength is displayed using a color gradient, with yellow indicating stronger associations while purple shades indicating weaker or no associations. This visualization highlights convergence points, gaps, and underrepresented linkages in the integration of genomics and biodiversity within One Health strategies in Kenya (see Text Box 1 for more details).

Sankey Diagram: Processes -> Stakeholder

Figure 2: The processes-stakeholder interactions reveal distributed relevance of each process to each stakeholder in the One Health framework. The diagram illustrates the interconnectedness between genomics enabled processes and various Kenyan institutions whose mandates include biodiversity, health, agriculture and policy. The columns on the left represent genomic processes that commence with field sampling, sequencing, annotation, functional profiling, risk assessment, surveillance integration, conservation action, agricultural advisory, export risk assessment, community outreach and access and benefit sharing. The columns on the right indicate the main institutions in Kenya with relevance to genomic processes. The thickness of the lines between the left and right columns indicate the strength and relevance of the interconnections between the processes and the stakeholder based on process priority, stakeholder's relevance, sectors, sector weight, process priority, and the quantity of species supplied as input as well as their relevance to the stakeholder and sectors respectively. On a scoping-level, the analysis shows that one of the most important stakeholders for biodiversity and genomics in Kenya is the National Museums of Kenya (NMK) followed by the Kenya Wildlife Service (KWS), indicating that the NMK and KWS are central hubs of the biodiversity genomic processes. This is an indication of the heavy involvement of the two institutions in sampling, biodiversity genomics, annotation conservation and ABS. In addition the KWS is seen as one of the core users of biodiversity, wildlife health and conservation related outputs. Other stakeholders also demonstrate linkages to the identified processes. The Directorate of Veterinary Services (DVS) shows links with antimicrobial resistance (AMR), surveillance integration and risk assessment while policy level engagements are shown from the Ministries of Agriculture, Tourism and Wildlife, Sports, Culture and Heritage and state corporations including Kenya Agricultural and Livestock Research Organisation and the National Environment Management Authority (NEMA). Risk assessment flows are also observed from the National Biosafety Authority (NBA), the Ministry of Agriculture and the NEMA. ILRI demonstrates a research-focused outlook especially in livestock and AMR. The Kenyan Ministry of Health, Kenyan National Public Health Institution, Kenyan Medical Research Institute, and the County Health Departments are shown in the diagram to play roles such as AMR, surveillance and sequencing for pathogen, public health, and human health related interventions. The Kenya Export Promotion and Branding Agency and the State Department for Trade indicate narrow but important links associated with export risk assessment and access and benefit-sharing. VF means Virulence Factor. The analysis was carried out on 152 Kenya species (introduced, native or endemic), both sequenced and unsequenced (see Text Box 1 for more details).

Chi-square association heatmap between selected categorical variables

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Figure 3: Selected categorical variables of species analysed reveals weak to moderate associations between variables. The diagram shows Chi-square heatmap between selected categorical variables (X- and Y- axis) with weak associations but stronger diagonal associations. The bar on the right shows a legend that depicts the degree of association linked by the colour intensity; yellow colour means weak association while dark blue means strong association. The numbers within each cell represent Chi-square test statistics, zero (0) means no association, close to zero means weak association, between 1500 - 2000 means moderate association while around 3000 or more means strong association. The genome assembly level (scaffold, contig, chromosome, and complete) show weak association with the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) and endemic status (introduced, native or endemic). However, ecological roles (for example, pathogen, predator, consumer) and taxonomic groups (e.g. livestock, reptiles, insects) show slightly moderate associations. The analysis was carried out on 152 Kenya species (introduced, native or endemic), both sequenced and unsequenced (see Text Box 1 for more details).

Figure 4: A scoping-level multi-layer One Health network reveals the interconnected between One Health stakeholders, processes, and selected unsequenced biodiversity in Kenya. The diagram shows a multi-layer One Health network involving eleven unsequenced biodiversity species (one per taxonomic group) or ecotypes and their process interactions with relevant One Health stakeholders. Blue nodes are selected species/ecotypes, magenta nodes are One Health stakeholders while green nodes are species/ecotypes. Grey lines delineate the interactions between species versus processes, and processes versus stakeholders. The analysis was carried out on 11 Kenya species (native), both sequenced and unsequenced (see Text Box 1 for more details).

Four years of building large-scale awareness and strengthening capacities in biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics across Africa

Between 2022 and 2025 the AfricaBP Open Institute organized 107 workshops across 12 African countries with particular focus on biodiversity genome sequencing, bioinformatics analysis, molecular biology and related fields, sample collection and biobanking, and ethical, legal, and social issues, playing a pivotal role in advancing genomics and bioinformatics innovations in Africa (Figure 4). About 90% of AfricaBP Open Institute workshops are sponsored by African organisations with around 10% sponsored by non-African organisations. The inaugural workshops in 2022, which were held virtually only and centrally coordinated, attracted around 700 registered participants, trained 22 African researchers and marked the beginning of a continent-wide knowledge exchange platform, focusing on biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics, and the establishment of operational guidelines and standardized training procedures (Figure 4) (Sharaf et al., 2023). These early efforts laid the foundation for a more structured and expansive programme in subsequent years, transforming the workshops into regionally coordinated hybrid (in-person and virtual), hub and spoke models (Figure 4) (Hayah et al., 2025).

By 2023, AfricaBP had scaled its activities significantly, delivering 28 workshops across 11 African countries, reaching over 3,700 participants from 80 countries globally (49 were African countries) and providing hands-on training to more than 400 scientists of whom more than 40% were women (Figure 4) (Sharaf et al., 2024). In 2024, the initiative expanded further, hosting 31 workshops with over 3500 participants from 67 countries (50 were African countries) (Figure 4) (Hayah et al., 2025). The content broadened to include advanced molecular biology technologies, gene editing, and stronger linkages between biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics and national bioeconomy strategies. This period solidified the workshops as a cornerstone for capacity -building and -strengthening, community and infrastructure development, and policy engagement across Africa. In 2025 the AfricaBP Open Institute organised 45 workshops that attracted around 5000 registered attendees from 75 countries globally (49 were African countries) that trained 545 African researchers through hands-on practicals (Figure 4 and Text Box 2).

Building on these achievements, the AfricaBP Open Institute 2025 regional workshops represented a strategic evolution rather than mere expansion. The format has been standardized under AfricaBP's Constitution and ByLaws, ensuring each African geographical region hosts an annual regional workshop that blends symposia, policy dialogue, and intensive practical training through hub and spoke model (African BioGenome Project, 2025b). The workshops also integrated advanced sequencing platforms while maintaining a commitment to inclusivity through free participation and

hybrid accessibility. Furthermore, ethical, legal, social considerations, and data sovereignty are central components of AfricaBP, ensuring that scientific advancements align with local and regional governance frameworks (AfricaBP Ethical, Legal and Social Issues Subcommittee, 2025; Katee et al., 2024). Additionally, thematic areas now align more deliberately with societal priorities such as livelihoods, sustainable ecosystem management, and OneHealth reflecting a maturing vision that goes beyond technical training.

Figure 4: The AfricaBP Open Institute has demonstrated consistent year-on-year growth across key indicators of its annual workshops. The AfricaBP Open Institute has attracted over 13,000 registered participants across at least 80 countries globally and trained over 1300 African researchers in genomics, bioinformatics, and related fields, in 2022 (Sharaf et al., 2023), 2023 (Sharaf et al., 2024), 2024 (Hayah et al., 2025), and 2025 (this paper; see Figure S1 - S5), enabling wider reach of its activities across all African countries. **A) Registered participants:** The number of registered participants increased from 700 in 2022 to 4,980 in 2025, reflecting sustained expansion of outreach and engagement across Africa. **B) Countries of origin:** Geographic diversity remained high, ranging from 50 countries in 2022 to a peak of 80 countries in 2023, with consistently broad continental representations. **C) Workshops held:** The number of regional and thematic workshops increased considerably from two in 2022 to forty-four in 2025, indicating a rapid increase in training and coordination activities. **D) Partners and sponsors:** The institutional support expanded from four partners in 2022 to 62 in 2025, indicating an increase in multi-stakeholder engagements and partnerships. **E) Persons trained:** The number of participants trained increased from 21 in 2022 to 545 in 2025, indicating a substantial enhancement in the capacity-building initiatives within the programme. Trend analysis was initially carried out using Python and Pandas for analysing statistics, with visualization in matplotlib and seaborn. Further (and final) analysis and visualisation was carried out using Tidyplots v0.3.1 which was implemented in R v4.4.1.

Current understanding of African One Health strategies through the lens of biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics

The AfricaBP Open Institute regional workshops in 2025 were organised as described in Sharaf et al (Sharaf et al., 2024) over a five-day period comprising two days of symposium-style conference and three days hands-on practical sessions across all five African geographical regions: West Africa (coordinated by the University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria and held from 5th to 9th May), East and Central Africa (coordinated by Mount Kenya University, Kenya, from 4th to 8th August), Southern Africa (coordinated by the South African Medical Research Council (SAMRC), South Africa, from 8th to 12th September), and North Africa (coordinated by Mohammed V University (UM5), Rabat , Morocco from 27th to 31st October) (Figure S1, S2, S3, and Text Box 2). We performed a synthetic review of all presentations (oral, poster, keynotes, invited guests) made at the four regional workshops and categorised them into nine (9) thematic areas which overlap with the AfricaBP's grand challenges (Ebenezer et al., 2022; Hayah et al., 2025; Sharaf et al., 2024), three global One Health themes (Brown et al., 2024) and an Artificial Intelligence thematic area, namely:

- *Genomics and bioinformatics technologies for the agri-environment:* The contribution of genomics and bioinformatics to agri-environmental innovation in Africa is accelerating advances in gene editing using CRISPR/CAS9 by enabling targeted modifications of plant and animal genomes to increase resilience under increasingly variable climatic and ecological conditions (Amoah et al., 2024). These include modifying genes to generate pathogen-resistant banana lines (Tripathi et al., 2019; Tripathi et al., 2020, 2021), increasing micronutrient contents through edits that elevate beta-carotene, iron or zinc accumulation, and the development of crops with improved nitrogen use efficiency, drought tolerance and extended post-harvest longevity (Kaur et al., 2020). These interventions collectively illustrate how precision genomics can reduce input dependence, stabilise yields and lower post-harvest losses in resource-constrained environments. Coupled with these innovations, bioinformatics plays a central role, providing the analytical foundation for identifying candidate genes for downstream analysis, mapping regulatory networks and predicting off-target effects (Mu et al., 2022). Genomic data are increasingly used to characterise plant–pathogen interactions, prioritise targets for editing and inform breeding pipelines (Bhadauria & Zhao, 2024; Dolatabadian & Fernando, 2022; Ogbuji & Agogbua, 2025). Emerging applications extend beyond productivity, with engineered plants and microbes being explored for environmental remediation and soil restoration (Jansson et al., 2023). Regulatory readiness with robust biosafety frameworks, data infrastructure and sustained capacity building to ensure responsible deployment is fundamental to

agri-environmental innovation (Rabuma et al., 2024). Together, these developments position genomics-enabled technologies as critical tools for strengthening agricultural resilience and advancing environmental sustainability across Africa (Tripathi et al., 2022).

- *Crops and livestock improvements and health:* Genomics and bioinformatics hold significant potential for improving crop and livestock health within the One Health framework in Africa (Ghazal et al., 2021; Ncube et al., 2025). By leveraging genomic technologies, researchers have gained insights into pathogen evolution, transmission dynamics, host-pathogen interactions, and development of effective vaccines and diagnostics (Tegally et al., 2022), which are crucial for developing targeted interventions and improving agricultural productivity (Nakayinga et al., 2024; Welgemoed et al., 2023). The application of these technologies has led to the identification of genetic markers associated with enhanced disease resistance and improved nutritional quality in crops such as in Kabuli chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) (Roorkiwal et al., 2020) and Moroccan Argan tree (*Argania spinosa*) (Alami et al., 2024; Idrissi et al., 2025; Khayi et al., 2020), facilitated marker-assisted selection and breeding programs in livestock (Akinsola et al., 2024; Houaga et al., 2023). Also, genomic insights is guiding the development of livestock and fish breeds with improved nutritional profiles, benefiting human health (Huang et al., 2025) as being exemplified at the University of South Africa through its indigenous livestock genomics efforts (Nesengani et al., 2025).
- *Genomics for the conservation of endangered and endemic species:* Growing genomic research on Africa's endemic and endangered species is providing critical insights into their evolutionary history, adaptive potential, and vulnerabilities (Colangelo et al., 2024; Prost et al., 2022), thereby demanding more integrated conservation interventions. Recent genomic studies on the population structure and phylogeography of African wildlife (Talenti et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2024) have catalyzed species cataloguing efforts, offering a genomic foundation for safeguarding intra-species diversity. Institutions such as the Ethiopian Biodiversity Institute (EBI) have established state-of-the-art laboratories to advance studies on genetic diversity, biosafety assessments of genetically modified crops, and the conservation of threatened genetic resources (Gebrhud et al., 2025; Gudaye et al., 2025). Similarly, the International Livestock Institute based in Kenya and Ethiopia applies genomics and bioinformatics to enhance livestock production with the goal of increasing food security and reducing poverty (Marshall et al., 2019). These national and regional efforts are also supported by collaborations with international sequencing platforms and organizations, enabling local sequencing capacity and genomic analyses. For example, in South Africa, the 1KSA initiative is sequencing diverse genomes to

develop targeted conservation strategies that protect endangered species and ensure their survival (DIPLOMICS, 2025a; Meyer et al., 2025) while the South African Medical Research Council is sequencing endemic African plants with conservation and medicinal significance (van Coller, 2025b). The continent is shifting towards genomics-enabled conservation initiatives that will enable African countries to better protect their unique biodiversity while strengthening resilience against ecological and climatic threats. The Sanger Tree of Life is working towards creating a foundational biological knowledge of all species in Britain, Northern Ireland and beyond, to support future innovation in biodiversity conservation, the bioeconomy, and biotechnological applications relevant to human and animal health (Howard et al., 2025). This approach demonstrates how large-scale biodiversity genomics can provide strategic resources for downstream policy development and innovation. Similarly, in Brazil, genomic tools are used to inform biodiversity conservation and promote the bioeconomy through the integration of genomics into public policy and ecosystem management for both flora and fauna (Vilaça et al., 2024).

- *Ethical, legal, socio-economics, and policy issues:* The acceleration of genomic research, digital sequencing, and AI-driven analytics in Africa raises profound ethical and socio-economic questions that directly shape the continent's ability to benefit from its biodiversity (Akpoviri et al., 2023). Despite being the primary source of global genetic diversity, Africa continues to lose value along the genomic value chain due to structural inequities, weak access and benefit-sharing implementations, and persistent data colonialism (Couvreur et al., 2021; Ebenezer et al., 2022). Digital Sequence Information (DSI) presents new governance challenges: While African biodiversity is frequently sequenced and uploaded into open databases (Marks et al., 2021), downstream products such as vaccines, diagnostics, breeding tools, and commercial bio-innovations are largely developed and patented outside the continent (Mulumba et al., 2025). This disconnect reflects a broader failure to align open science with equity, Indigenous data sovereignty, and fair benefit-sharing. At policy level, fragmentation across global regulatory regimes complicates compliance and creates loopholes that undermine fairness in access and use (Ebert et al., 2023). Socio-economically, these governance gaps disproportionately affect communities that steward Africa's livestock and biodiversity, including pastoralists, smallholders, and Indigenous Peoples, who face genetic erosion, climate stress, and exclusion from emerging commercial genomics markets (Gollin, 2020; Houaga et al., 2023). Strengthening ethical practice requires Africa-led genomic governance models grounded in Free, Prior, and Informed Consent, CARE principles, community-embedded consent systems, and

transparent value-tracking across the genomic lifecycle (El Allali et al., 2024; Katee et al., 2024; Munung et al., 2021).

- *Technology development, knowledge exchange, industry, and commercialization:* The integration and advancement of genomic tools such as metagenomics, portable sequencing, and progressive pipelines using advanced statistical models are key factors that contribute to creating a more resilient Africa by improving surveillance, preparedness, and response to health emergencies (Kanzi et al., 2025). Portable sequencers are now commonly used for outbreak response, and routine monitoring of viral and pathogen threats, allowing regional centres to perform near-real-time genomic epidemiology (Bastug et al., 2025). This approach was applied during outbreaks such as SARS-CoV-2 and Ebola, and is a core component of modern One Health surveillance (Bastug et al., 2025; Musila, 2022). A substantial and rising commercial opportunity is emerging in Africa at the crossroads of One Health and biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics, with current markets for sequencing, environmental DNA (eDNA) surveillance, bioinformatics solutions, and translational research and developments already in place (Hayah et al., 2025).
- *Zoonoses and emerging diseases:* The intersection of biodiversity genomics and One Health is emerging as a critical frontier for addressing zoonoses and emerging diseases (Gebreyes et al., 2014; Inzaule et al., 2021). Although regional genomic networks such as the Africa CDC Pathogen Genomics Initiative have increasingly enhanced human and animal pathogen genomic surveillance on the continent (Gebreyes et al., 2014; Inzaule et al., 2021), biodiversity and ecosystems genomics and bioinformatics knowledge systems remain underutilized in risk prediction and early detection (Carroll et al., 2021; Kuhn et al., 2024). Ecological degradation, habitat fragmentation, and climate variability are reshaping host-pathogen-environment interactions across the continent (Wilkinson et al., 2018). Continuous monitoring of ecosystem health across the continent is key to limiting hazardous interfaces between humans, livestock, and wildlife reservoirs of zoonotic diseases (Gibb et al., 2020), but most African One Health frameworks, while progressively integrating genomics and bioinformatics approaches, still emphasize epidemic preparedness and outbreak response (see Table 1) rather than continuous monitoring of ecosystem health across Africa.

Scientific networks are beginning to bridge this gap through nonprofit initiatives such as the Open Science Community Nigeria (OSCN) (Ahmad & Bobbo, 2023) that promote transparent scientific practice and expand access to training in bioinformatics and data analysis, strengthening the regional knowledge base required for a genomics-informed One Health approach. In East Africa, Makerere

University (Akurut et al., 2025), Mount Kenya University (Kuja et al., 2022) and the Ethiopian research institutions (Islam et al., 2023; Mandefro et al., 2024; Tesfaye et al., 2022) are applying reverse vaccinology, pathogen genomics, and computational approaches to accelerate vaccine discovery and strengthen multisectoral disease prevention strategies aligned with One Health initiatives. These efforts align with wider regional and continental aspirations to meet international standards for biosafety, biodiversity protection, and sustainable development championed by the Africa Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (Africa CDC) (Maruta et al., 2023) and other national associations such as the Moroccan Association of Biosafety, Biosecurity, and Health Security (AMBS) (Bajjou et al., 2019). Collectively, these initiatives reflect a continental shift toward embedding biodiversity genomics within One Health, reinforcing Africa's capacity to anticipate emerging infectious threats while advancing climate resilience, ecological conservation, and socioeconomic stability (Kajumbula et al., 2024; Ochola, 2025).

- *Anti-microbial resistance*: Genomics and bioinformatics have become key in understanding and fighting antimicrobial resistance as the tools show how microbial resistance genes are propagating and persisting in the microbial population (Nguinkal et al., 2024). Genetic modification and genome editing technologies are essential for promoting the One Health agenda in sub-Saharan Africa, where the health of people, animals, and the environment are closely linked (Akinbo et al., 2025). Anti-microbial resistance (AMR) constitutes a significant One Health challenge in North Africa, particularly affecting agriculture, food security, and public health coverage. Studies on the inaugural comprehensive genomic characterization of *Salmonella gallinarum* isolated from poultry in Morocco offers essential insight into this matter (Farhat et al., 2025). The methodology employs mapping resistance genes and mutations, pointing out the value of genetic and bioinformatics technologies in AMR surveillance and emphasizing the necessity for antimicrobial stewardship, enhanced biosecurity, and cohesive policies between veterinary and public health sectors (Farhat et al., 2025).
- *Climate health*: The relationship between climate change and the well-being of living organisms, particularly human populations, continues to intensify across the continents and has become one of the most pressing threats to societal resilience and community well-being in Africa (Sintayehu, 2018; Wright et al., 2024). Hence, the issue of climate health has become one of the core thematic areas of its focus. Ecological stability and its resilience to changing environments are central to health. Habitat diversity helps to combat the increased burden of emerging challenges and supports the genetic and species diversity, which

ensures resilience to stress and resistance to pests and pathogens (Bourdin et al., 2022; van Emden & Dabrowski, 1994).

- *Genomic language models*: Genomic language models (gLMs) offer powerful new tools for interpreting biological sequences, their functions, and advancing genomic research across sectors (Ji et al., 2021). By enabling rapid analysis of pathogens, antimicrobial-resistance genes, and host–microbe interactions, they strengthen integrated human, animal, and environmental health surveillance within the One Health framework (Djordjevic et al., 2024). Treating DNA as a learnable biological language allows gLMs to decode regulatory grammar, motifs, chromatin context, and evolutionary signals (Akotenou & El Allali, 2025; Ji et al., 2021). Training transformer models on nucleotide sequences enables inference of promoters, enhancers, transcription-factor logic, and the functional impact of genetic variants (Avsec et al., 2021). Emerging architectures further extend these capabilities by incorporating long-range dependencies and multi-omic data. In microbial genomics, for example, a gLM-based model such as GeneLM developed at the University Mohammed VI Polytechnic in Morocco improves gene prediction and surpasses traditional tools in identifying coding sequences and translation initiation sites, with attention maps that highlight biologically meaningful motifs (Akotenou & El Allali, 2025). Together, these advances demonstrate how AI-driven genomic modeling can enhance biological interpretation and support data-driven health decision-making.

Summary of course contents of selected practical workshops

Here, we summarise what is new in the hands-on practical workshops hosted during the regional workshops 2025 series (Figure S1 and Table 2). New, here, describes entities involved or key processes and products used for the first time since the establishment of the AfricaBP Open Institute regional workshops in 2023 (for descriptions of all course contents please see Table 2). We bin these new activities into two categories and referenced the relevant practicals (see Table 2 for details):

1. *New hands-on practical sites or locations*: Several new practical sites include University of Ain Temouchent and Genethical in *Algeria*, the American University in Cairo (AUC) in *Egypt*, Hawassa University in *Ethiopia*, Change Biotec and Jomo Kenya University of Agriculture and Technology (JKUAT) in *Kenya*, A.P. Leventis Ornithological Research Institute (APLORI), National Biotechnology Research and Development Agency (NBRDA), and University of Calabar in *Nigeria*, South African Medical Research Council (SAMRC), DIPLOMICS, and CenGen in *South Africa*, and University of Lome in *Togo*.

2. *New technologies, tools, and techniques:* Some new technologies, tools or techniques featured include DNBSEQ T7 genome sequencer by SAMRC and MGI (South Africa) (van Coller, 2025a), NextFlow (Di Tommaso et al., 2017) by SAMRC, Mohammed V University in Rabat (Morocco), Institut Pasteur Tunis (Tunisia), Nile University (Egypt), and Inqaba Biotec East Africa (Kenya), chemoinformatics in drug discovery workshop by SAMRC, plant photogrammetry by University of Ain Temouchent (Algeria), morphometric analysis using MorphoJ by University of Abou Bekr Belkaid Tlemcen (Algeria), and DArT-seq by Hawassa University (Ethiopia).

Table 2: Summary of course contents of selected practical workshops during the practical sessions of the AfricaBP Open Institute regional workshops 2025

S/N	Practical session thematic area	AfricaBP regional workshop	Name of practical host organisation and country of affiliation	Title of hands-on practical session held	Summary of course content
1	Ethical, legal and social issues (ELSI)	Southern Africa	South African Medical Research Center (SAMRC), South Africa	Ethics, Legal, and Social Implications in African Genomics Research	<p>This workshop provided real cases and practical exercises that traced the full pathway of sample collections and ELSI from consent to custodianship, examining how ethical foundations, regulatory frameworks, and benefit-sharing mechanisms must align to protect communities, uphold sovereignty, and ensure genomic research is fair, lawful, and equitable. The module began by establishing the ethical architecture of research through scenario-based prompts and discussions on the responsibilities that arise <i>before the first sample collection, first research publication and/or first patent</i>, are made for any biological species. Participants explored key ethical considerations including genuine Prior Informed Consent (PIC), publication authorship and recognition, ownership of genetic resources and Digital Sequence Information (DSI), and justice in benefit-sharing. Using the AfricaBP ELSI framework (AfricaBP Ethical, Legal and Social Issues Subcommittee, 2025; Katee et al., 2024), this workshop emphasized an ethics–law–society compass that links consent, compliance, and community trust. The workshop used landmark biopiracy cases including San–Hoodia, Rooibos, and <i>Prunus africana</i>, to delineate how weak consent processes, vague Material Transfer Agreements (MTAs), and inequitable IP regimes, enable exploitation and sideline Indigenous custodians. It then grounded participants in the legal architecture governing genomics, from the Nagoya and Cartagena Protocols to national access and benefit-sharing and biosafety requirements, applying these</p>

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					tools through real-world regulatory scenarios involving PIC, Mutually Agreed Terms, permits, MTAs, Data Sharing Agreements, and DSI sovereignty, and risk assessment.
2	Cheminformatics	Southern Africa	South African Medical Research Center (SAMRC), South Africa	Cheminformatics in drug discovery workshop	This workshop provided a focused platform for advancing computational strategies that support rational, data-driven drug development. Participants explored the integration of cheminformatics and bioinformatics to strengthen early decision-making, beginning with predictive ADMET profiling, <i>in silico</i> toxicity predictions, and computational pharmacokinetic screening to prioritise compounds efficiently. A key component of the workshop was biological target identification and structural analysis, where trainees engaged with protein libraries and performed homology modelling using both traditional approaches and AlphaFold (Jumper et al., 2021) to generate high-confidence structural predictions. These models formed the foundation for molecular docking workflows conducted with AutoDock Vina (Eberhardt et al., 2021; Trott & Olson, 2010) and H-dock (Yan et al., 2017), enabling protein-ligand and protein-protein interaction analyses, docking validation, and interpretation of interaction maps. Practical sessions reinforced best practices in ligand optimization, active-site definition, and the use of online docking servers for virtual screening. The workshop underscored the essential role of integrated cheminformatics-bioinformatics pipelines in accelerating modern drug discovery.
3	Genome sequencing and bioinformatics	East and Central Africa	F&S Scientific Ltd, Kenya	Molecular and NGS workflows	The two day NGS training provided theoretical and practical exposure to nucleic acid extraction, fragment analysis and sequencing workflows. Participants gained experience in manual and automated DNA extraction

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	analysis				using Norgen Biotek Kits and Tanbead systems, they assessed nucleic acid quality with the BiOptic Qsep1 platform. Sessions covered Illumina sequencing workflows from sample prep, library preparation, sequencing and data analysis (using DRAGEN solution). A data analysis demo presentation using DRAGEN Microbial Enrichment Plus (DME+) Application via Illumina BaseSpace Hub was performed.
4	Genome sequencing and bioinformatics analysis	North Africa	Biosciences CoreLab, Mohamed VI Polytechnic University (UM6P), Morocco	Illumina sequencing of Moroccan plant species	An intensive three-day hands-on and theoretical workshop dedicated to Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)-free library preparation for Whole Genome Sequencing on the NovaSeq X Plus platform. This workshop combined in-depth methodological training with practical laboratory sessions, guiding participants through every step of high-quality library construction, from sample quality control and fragmentation to adapter ligation, cleanup, and final library validation and pooling. Participants also gained a comprehensive understanding of the principles behind the PCR-free workflow, its advantages for variant accuracy, and best practices for high-throughput sequencing on the NovaSeq X Plus.
5	Genome sequencing and bioinformatics analysis	East and Central Africa	Change Biotec, Kenya	Genomics: DNA sequencing of <i>Apis mellifera</i> (Honey bee) using ONT-Ligation Sequencing Kit V14 protocol	The two-day workshop, organised in partnership with the Africa Genomics Center and Consultancy, focused on <i>High-Molecular-Weight DNA Sequencing of Apis mellifera</i> introduced participants to end-to-end nanopore sequencing workflows using the Oxford Nanopore Technology (ONT) Ligation Sequencing Kit V14. Participants performed library preparation, loading, and sequencing, followed by bioinformatics analysis involving quality control (FastQC, NanoPlot, PycoQC), genome assembly (minimap2, Flye, Canu), polishing (bcftools), annotation (Funannotate), and

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					quality assessment (BUSCO, QUAST).
6	Genome sequencing and bioinformatics analysis	North Africa	Faculty of Sciences of Tunis, University of Tunis El Manar, Tunisia	From barcode to biosurveillance: Hands-on species ID for biodiversity and e-Health using ONTbarcoder 2.0.	This practical workshop provided an intensive three-day, practice-oriented exercises that focused on hands-on laboratory and bioinformatic activities for species identification. Participants carried out sample preparation, nucleic acid extraction, PCR amplification, barcoded primer design, gel electrophoresis, and MinION-compatible library preparation. Participants also conducted live Oxford Nanopore MinION sequencing runs, assessed data quality, and processed sequencing outputs using ONTbarcoder 2.0 (Srivathsan et al., 2024) for demultiplexing and species identification. Troubleshooting and optimization sessions reinforced technical skills throughout the workshop. Applied modules exposed participants to real case studies involving wildlife, parasite, and pathogen barcoding for biosurveillance. In addition, trainees practiced submitting data to BOLD and GenBank and developed collaborative mini-projects related to biodiversity monitoring and eDNA applications.
7	Genome sequencing and bioinformatics analysis	East and Central Africa	Inqaba Biotec East Africa, Kenya	Understanding biodiversity through Sanger sequencing and NextFlow workflow manager for big data	This workshop combined hands-on sessions focused on DNA sequencing and molecular identification of pathogens and species using Sanger sequencing and analysis of NGS data using NextFlow analysis tool. Participants were able to demonstrate practical abilities in molecular techniques and were introduced to the principles of Sanger sequencing, from PCR amplification of target genomic regions to quality control using the nano-drop quantification method. Practical sessions involved DNA extraction from a non-biting midge, a type of fly common in the shores of Lake Victoria in Kenya. Using the Zymo tissue-insect kit (Zymo research,

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					California, USA), samples were amplified, and cycle sequenced using the Nimagen Brilliant dye v3.1 (Nimagen, Netherlands) and the data was cleaned. The workshop emphasized selecting genomic regions that balance conservation and variability to distinguish species of the two insects. The NextFlow (Di Tommaso et al., 2017) session introduced participants to workflow managers, containerization tools (Docker) using the Python programming language. NGS data in FASTQ format was parsed and quality checks done with FastQC and MultiQC. Participants were taken through the high throughput library (HTS lib) (Danecek et al., 2021) pipeline and were able to annotate for functional genes from the sequences and build a phylogeny.
8	Genome sequencing and bioinformatics analysis	Southern Africa	Inqaba Biotec, South Africa	PacBio Revio HiFi sequencing	This workshop introduced participants to PacBio HiFi sequencing, describing key performance characteristics of HiFi sequencing and its advantages, understanding the HiFi sequencing workflow, key consumable products and various HiFi sequencing applications.
9	Genome sequencing and bioinformatics analysis	Southern Africa	Separations, South Africa	Illumina Next Generation Sequencing: DNA to data	Hosted by Separations at the Centre for Epidemic Response and Innovation, this workshop introduced participants to both theoretical and practical aspects of DNA isolation and purification from plant samples using the Macherey-Nagel NucleoSpin Plant kit (Macherey-Nagel, Germany). Participants also learnt how to perform quality assessments in order to ensure high quality nucleic acids suitable for downstream library preparation. Following this, participants were trained on whole genome sequencing library preparation using the Illumina DNA Prep PCR Free kit. The resulting libraries were quantified, pooled by mass, and prepared for

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					sequencing on the Illumina NextSeq 2000 with a 2 x 150 bp configuration. Finally, the workshop concluded with an interactive exercise demonstrating genome assembly using the Illumina BaseSpace Sequence Hub.
10	Genome sequencing and bioinformatics analysis	Southern Africa	DIPLOMICS, South Africa	1KSA library preparation and sequencing	The 1KSA Library Prep and Sequencing workshop was offered jointly by staff from DIPLOMICS and the University of Pretoria. The focus was on ONT library preparation and whole genome sequencing on a PromethION sequencer, using the 1KSA workflow (DIPLOMICS, 2025b). In this three day workshop, participants were guided through an introduction to the 1KSA project, ONT sequencing technology, DNA quality control, purification and end-repair, library preparation using the ligation kit, flow cell loading and sequencing. Each participant had an opportunity to build their own library using a 1KSA sample and load their own flow cell. In addition, participants were taught how to interpret the resulting sequencing run report and an overview of the 1KSA data analysis pipeline was provided. Participants were also introduced to other ONT sequencing kits and community resources available on the ONT website.
11	Genome sequencing and bioinformatics analysis	Southern Africa	South African Medical Research Council (SAMRC) Genomics Platform, South Africa	WGS with DNBSEQ-T7	The three day workshop introduced participants to whole genome sequencing (WGS) on the DNBSEQ T7. Day 1: Participants underwent theory training on best practices of DNBSEQ technology, followed by sample quality assessment, sample normalization, and operation of the automated platform MGISP-960 for library preparation. Day 2: the workshop encompassed quality control of the libraries and best practices for pooling multiple libraries for ultra-high-throughput sequencing. Day 3: Instrument operation for sequencing with DNBSEQ T7, PE 150, using dual

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					indexing approach. The workshop combined theoretical sessions with wet-lab hands-on training, highlighting the importance of an error-free library construction approach with DNBSEQ technology and its importance in accurate detection of SNPs and small insertions/deletions for better resolution of genetic diversity data, especially for the scope of focus of the workshop (genetic diversity of African lions). This was followed by an online session to review the summary report, with over 6000 million reads per flow cell, and a quality score of Q30 > 97%.
12	Genome sequencing and Bioinformatics analysis	Southern Africa	North-West University, South Africa	UESM sequencing platform - ONT	The workshop was focused on equipping participants with practical skills in sample preparation, sequencing workflows and bioinformatics analysis relevant to environmental genomics. The introductory lectures introduced the ONT technology and its applications in environmental sciences, with case studies on agriculture, aquatic ecosystem health, climate change research, and integration into the Unit for Environmental Sciences and Management (UESM) research projects. The participants were trained on basic molecular techniques, which included DNA quantitation (fragment analysis and quantification using different methods (spectrophotometer, gel electrophoresis), PCR amplification and sample dilutions for downstream processing. The second day introduced library preparation for bacterial and fungal genomes sequencing on the ONT platforms. To develop capacity in bioinformatics, the trainers focused on basecalling, quality control, assembly, and quality control of ONT data. The analyses were performed both via command line (Linux through the CHPC) and on open-source web-based platforms (Galaxy, Kbase).

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13	Genome sequencing and bioinformatics analysis	North Africa	The American University in Cairo, Egypt	Exploring genomic diversity - hands-on workshop in plant genome sequencing and bioinformatics	The workshop provided an intensive hands-on training experience in plant genome sequencing and bioinformatics. The first three days focused on wet-lab skills, guiding participants through the complete workflow from field samples to sequencing. Activities included DNA extraction using the CTAB method (Li et al., 2013), quality assessment with Nanodrop (Aboul-Maaty & Oraby, 2019), Qubit (Shim et al., 2024), gel electrophoresis, and an introduction to Illumina sequencing chemistry. Participants then prepared sequencing libraries through tagmentation, cleanup, indexing PCR, and quantification, followed by library pooling and running an Illumina MiSeq instrument. The final two days introduced participants to comparative plant genomics, emphasizing SNP-based diversity between African and non-African species. Trainees learned essential and comprehensive bioinformatics skills, including genome data processing, including retrieval, quality control, read trimming, alignment, variant calling, and functional annotation with tools such as SnpEff.
14	Genome sequencing and bioinformatics analysis	North Africa	Genethical Laboratory & GenApAgiE Laboratory, University of Tlemcen, Algeria	From extraction to bioinformatics analysis: NGS application	This intensive three-day workshop provided a comprehensive, end-to-end practical training in Next-Generation Sequencing. The curriculum began with theoretical foundations of NGS workflows (Ion Torrent) and anatomical pathology. Participants then performed hands-on DNA extraction using an EZ2 automated system, library preparation, and templating. The course culminated in a bioinformatics practical session, where attendees launched the sequencing pipeline, performed data analysis, and interpreted results under expert supervision, enabling them to independently manage a complete NGS project from sample to insight.

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15	Genome editing	North Africa	African Genome Center (AGC), University Mohammed VI Polytechnic (UM6P), Morocco	CRISPR fundamentals II program and protocols 2025	The goal of this workshop is to demystify the CRISPR technology and show the participants how to put it into practice. Participants worked with both cloning-based and cloning-free CRISPR approaches: designing and cloning gRNAs targeting OsNAS1, OsVIT1 OsVIT2 and OsBCHX in rice with the cloning based technique, and performing CRISPR edits on the HPRT gene in mouse genomic DNA with the cloning-free technique. Participants also learned the assessment of the outcome of their edits, by analyzing CRISPR-modified samples and interpreting editing efficiency and precision. The workshop was concluded with a hands-on pipetting training session offered by Eppendorf. The session covered proper pipette handling, accuracy techniques, and best laboratory practices. Thermo Fisher Scientific also gave an overview of CRISPR technology—from guide RNA design and transfection to edit validation—highlighting key tools, troubleshooting tips, and practical examples. Finally, GenScript complemented the session by presenting its GenCRISPR platform.
16	Bioinformatics analysis only	Southern Africa	South African Medical Research Center (SAMRC), South Africa	An introduction to NextFlow	The workshop offered a theoretical overview of Nextflow alongside practical training. Briefly, participants were introduced to the concepts of bioinformatics reproducibility and the importance of open science, using the Nextflow workflow management system and nf-core pipelines (Di Tommaso et al., 2017) as an illustrative example. This introduction led participants to acquire the skills needed for installing, configuring, and executing an nf-core pipeline using default test data. On the second day, participants delved into understanding the fundamental components of an nf-core pipeline and the requirements for configuring and executing

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					pipelines with their own data. The third day covered more advanced topics, focusing on the development of custom modules and pipelines utilising an nf-core template and individual scripts. Finally, participants received training in troubleshooting approaches and were introduced to the Seqera platform as a supplementary method for visually tracing and debugging their pipelines.
17	Bioinformatics analysis only	Western Africa	Inqaba Biotec West Africa, Nigeria	Intermediate bioinformatics	This was hands-on training on NGS data analysis. The participants gained practical expertise in Linux environment, bioinformatics, file structures. They processed data using fastQC and Trimomatic and proceeded to read alignment to reference genomes using BWA and SAMtools, further processed the data for variant detection and carried out annotation using GATK. Participants conducted protein sequence and structural analysis, explored protein-protein interaction networks and performed phylogenetic inference with MrBayes. Working with fungal genomics datasets, trainees implemented end-to-end analytical pipelines, reinforcing their competency in high throughput data processing and integrative bioinformatics interpretation.
18	Bioinformatics analysis only	North Africa	Faculty of Sciences, Mohammed V University in Rabat, Morocco	Nextflow and nf-core: RNA-seq training workshop	The workshop introduced participants to a complete RNA-seq analysis workflow, moving from conceptual foundations to practical implementation in a NextFlow execution environment (Di Tommaso et al., 2017). The sessions outlined principles of experimental design, sequencing read structure, alignment principles, and transcript-level quantification. Participants then executed the nf-core/rnaseq pipeline in a containerized Docker environment (Ewels et al., 2020; Harshil Patel et al., 2025; Merkel,

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					2014), beginning with quality control using FastQC (Andrews et al., 2010) and read trimming with Trim Galore (Krueger, 2015), followed by alignment with HISAT2 (Kim et al., 2019). The training supported reproducible and standardized workflow management, and participants gained experience interpreting outputs, including QC summaries, trimming reports, alignment statistics, and a comprehensive MultiQC report (Ewels et al., 2016), alongside gene-level count matrices generated for downstream analysis.
19	Bioinformatics analysis only	North Africa	Nile University, Egypt	Marine bioinformatics: biodiversity genomics, and Nextflow Pipelines	The aim of this workshop was advancing regional expertise in bioinformatics and genomic data analysis. Over three days, the program introduced participants to core concepts in biodiversity genomics, including 16S rRNA analysis, metagenomic workflows, and computational pipeline management using the Galaxy and Nextflow platforms. The workshop integrated lectures, practical exercises, and a structured hackathon, offering a comprehensive training model that balanced conceptual understanding with hands-on skill development. The interactive format promoted teamwork, discussion, and analytical thinking, enabling attendees to apply newly acquired techniques to authentic datasets. Representation from multiple Egyptian universities fostered a collaborative environment, supporting interdisciplinary learning and knowledge exchange among researchers at various career stages. The final project presentations demonstrated the participants' capacity to implement complex bioinformatics workflows and derive biologically meaningful interpretations.
20	Bioinformatics	East and	Laboratory of	NGS data	The curriculum covered the full spectrum of NGS analysis, including: 1)

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	analysis only	Central Africa	Molecular Biology, University of Kinshasa, DR Congo	analysis with Galaxy platform and linux	Platform setup: Introduction to the Galaxy platform and Linux basics (including WSL installation), 2) Data acquisition & quality control: Retrieving FASTQ data and performing quality checks using both Galaxy and Linux command lines (with tools like FASTQC and Trimmomatic), 3) Genome assembly & validation: Conducting assembly and assessing quality using both platforms (with tools like SPAdes).
21	Bioinformatics analysis only	East and Central Africa	National Animal Genetic Resources Center and Data Bank, Uganda	Tidying and analysis of biodiversity and ecological data in R	The workshop introduced participants to the complete workflow for analyzing biodiversity and ecological data in R, focusing on data importation, quality control, manipulation, and visualization. Using <i>tidyverse</i> (Wickham et al., 2019), alongside <i>ggstatsplot</i> (Patil, 2021), <i>lessR</i> (Gerbing, 2025), <i>table1</i> (Rich, 2025), and <i>flextable</i> (Gohel et al., 2025) packages, participants learned to perform structured data cleaning, statistical visualization, and preparation of publication-ready outputs. The approach combined conceptual discussions with live coding exercises, allowing participants to follow and apply each step in real time.
22	Bioinformatics analysis only	East and Central Africa	Pwani University, Kenya	DNA to Diversity: A hands-on introduction to African wildlife genomics	This workshop introduced participants to the practical and analytical foundations of African wildlife genomics, combining lectures with hands-on bioinformatics sessions, and covered key areas including next-generation sequencing (NGS) principles, population genomics, and metagenomics, using real genomic datasets to explore topics such as variant calling, relatedness estimation, heterozygosity analysis, and environmental DNA (eDNA) applications. Participants, drawn from academia and conservation, developed practical skills in data handling, command-line analysis, and

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					interpretation of genomic variation.
23	Bioinformatics analysis only	North Africa	Bioinformatics Laboratory, College of Computing, University Mohammed VI Polytechnic, Morocco	Annotation of repetitive sequences and transcription factor identification in plant genomes	The workshop provided an applied introduction to the identification and annotation of repetitive sequences in plant genomes. Participants learned core concepts of repetitive DNA, including their types, origins, and roles in plant genome structure. Practical sessions covered construction of repeat libraries using de novo and homology-based tools. The program also introduced Simple Sequence Repeats (SSRs), their applications in plant genetics, and workflows for identifying SSRs, designing SSR markers, and performing genotyping analyses. Hands-on activities included the use of MegaSSR (Morad M. Mokhtar et al., 2023), in silico PCR tools, and MegaPlantTF (Akotenou et al., 2026), an artificial intelligence based transcription factor identification platform. The final day focused on transposable elements, their classification, and their influence on genome evolution. Participants practiced identifying LTR retrotransposons with MegaLTR (Mokhtar & El Allali, 2023) and assessing genome assembly quality using PlantLAI (Morad M Mokhtar et al., 2023). The workshop concluded with an overview of additional bioinformatics tools and resources available at the laboratory's online platform (UM6P Bioinformatics Platform, 2025).
24	Bioinformatics analysis only	East and Central Africa	Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology, Kenya	Applied bioinformatics skills workshop (Linux, HPC, and genome	The workshop introduced participants to foundational bioinformatics skills, focusing on Linux operations, high-performance computing (HPC), and genome assembly workflows. Through a mix of lectures and hands-on exercises, participants learned to navigate command-line environments, manage computational jobs, and perform key steps in NGS data

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				assembly)	processing, including data download, quality control, read trimming, genome assembly, and assembly evaluation. Practical sessions used tools such as FastQC for quality assessment, Trimmomatic for data cleaning, SPAdes for genome assembly, and BUSCO for evaluating assembly completeness. Participants gained an understanding of how raw sequencing data are transformed into accurate genomic information and how to detect and correct assembly errors. The training effectively bridged wet-lab and computational genomics, enhancing participants' confidence to apply bioinformatics tools independently. Feedback highlighted the value of mentorship and the need for longer, more in-depth sessions and ongoing learning support to sustain and expand regional bioinformatics capacity.
25	Bioinformatics analysis only	North Africa	Institut Pasteur Tunis (IPT), Tunisia	Reproducible bioinformatics with Nextflow : applications in OMICS workshop	This workshop was designed to introduce the core principles of workflow development in bioinformatics using Nextflow, with the aim to equip participants with the necessary skills to build reproducible and scalable pipelines for increasingly complex omics analyses. The workshop introduced the syntax and structure of NextFlow scripts, providing a clear understanding of how to design modular and maintainable workflows, where participants learned how to handle various computational environments, ranging from the use of Conda for managing virtual environments to the deployment of containers such as Docker and Apptainer (Singularity), all within the Nextflow framework. A key component of the training, managing input and output configurations, was the initial step of learning to ensure modularity, scalability and reproducibility. Finally, participants have also been introduced to the nf-core initiatives and learned

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					how to execute existing validated, community-curated workflows that cover a wide range of omics applications (nf-core pipeline). By the end of the training, and as part of the workshop, participants were divided into groups where they developed different pipelines and presented them to all participants.
26	Bioinformatics analysis only	East and Central Africa	Addis Ababa University, Ethiopia	RNA-Seq analysis	The workshop focused on RNA-Seq analysis using the Galaxy Project platform, aiming to familiarize participants with basic RNA-Seq analysis workflows and pipelines. Participants received theoretical and hands-on practicals on RNA Seq data quality control, read mapping to reference genomes, mapping result interpretation, and visualization. The workshop also included an introduction to the Galaxy platform. The lecture sessions covered key topics including the role of genomics and bioinformatics in biodiversity conservation, an overview of RNA-Seq analysis, basic pipelines for quality assessment, genome mapping, feature count, differential gene expression analysis and visualization tools. The hands-on exercises guided participants through exploring Galaxy platform features, quality control, filtering, and trimming of sequencing data, sequence read mapping and assessment of mapping quality based on “Reference based RNA Seq analysis tutorial” (Batut et al., 2025).
27	Bioinformatics analysis only	Southern Africa	DIPLOMICS, South Africa	1KSA genome assembly workshop at DIPLOMICS	The workshop guided participants through each step of the 1KSA Genome Assembly Pipeline (DIPLOMICS-SA & Meiring, 2025) on the Centre for High Performance Computing (CHPC). Attendees began with basic Linux command-line training and learned how to work within the CHPC environment. They manually ran all stages of the workflow starting from

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					<p>raw fastq files (ONT), including k-mer counting with KMC (Kokot et al., 2017), quality checks with NanoPlot (De Coster & Rademakers, 2023), and filtering with NanoFilt (De Coster & Rademakers, 2023). Genome assemblies were generated using both Flye (Kolmogorov et al., 2019) and Hifiasm (Cheng et al., 2024), and their performance was directly compared using the same input dataset. Racon polishing was applied to Flye assemblies. Participants assessed assembly completeness with BUSCO (Tegenfeldt et al., 2025) and QUAST (Gurevich et al., 2013), and they also generated assembly statistics by running a script to create a detailed snail plot, along with learning how to interpret its more complex metrics. Finally, participants learned how to run the full automated pipeline hosted on GitHub, gaining practical experience in both individual command execution and end-to-end reproducible genome assembly workflows on an HPC system.</p>
28	Bioinformatics analysis only	West Africa	Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology (KNUST), Ghana	Eukaryotic genome assembly and annotation	<p>This training focused on techniques for assembling, annotating, and evaluating eukaryotic genomes utilizing long-read sequencing datasets from PacBio HiFi (Wenger et al., 2019) and ONT (Jain et al., 2018). The sessions included hands-on bioinformatics exercises, demonstrations, and engaging discussions. Participants, following a brief introduction to Linux commands, undertook the following activities: (1) tested various assembly algorithms (Hifiasm, Verkko, and LJA) (Bankevich et al., 2022; Cheng et al., 2021; Rautiainen et al., 2023), with an emphasis on parameter settings for each tool, (2) conducted assembly quality assessments using QUAST (Gurevich et al., 2013), gfastats (Formenti et al., 2022), asmgenes (Li, 2018), and Merqury (Rhie et al., 2020), (3) executed assembly cleanup and</p>

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					genome annotation using liftOff (Shumate & Salzberg, 2021), mashmap (for Long Read/Contig Mapping) (Kille et al., 2023), and minimap2 (Li, 2018). Lastly, we delved into phased assemblies, which represent the latest trend in Telomere-to-Telomere (T2T) assemblies.
29	Bioinformatics analysis only	East and Central Africa	Bioinformatics and Data Analytics Lab, Hawassa University, Ethiopia	DArT-seq data training	This practicals provided a specialized hands-on practical on DartSeq Generated GBS Data Filtering and Analysis. It addressed crucial modules, including fundamentals of R programming, Integrated Development Environment setup, and SNP data processing on Day 1. On Day 2 of the hands-on practicals, participants followed the SNP data processing and filtering algorithms for downstream analysis, and gained experience on reading DArT files (Meyer, 2019) into genlight objects as well as applying filtering algorithms for downstream analysis. The session addressed reproducibility, data integrity, and practical applications in plant genomics.
30	Basic molecular biology and bioinformatics analysis	West Africa	University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria	Practical approach to genomics	The program had two components: lectures and practicals. Day 1 of the practical workshop focused on basic techniques in molecular biology followed by practical exercises on pipetting and DNA extraction. Day 2 focused on lectures on PCR (principles and applications), primer design as well as wet lab sessions on PCR, gel preparations, loading, visualization and NanoDrop Spectrophotometry. Day 3 included practicals on basic bioinformatics, software installation, NCBI database, sequence alignment, and introduction to BLAST and phylogenetics.
31	Basic molecular biology and	West Africa	MyAfroDNA, Nigeria	Hands-on training on basic	This workshop introduced participants to essential laboratory techniques in molecular biology, including DNA extraction, PCR, gel electrophoresis, and

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	bioinformatics analysis			molecular biology techniques and bioinformatics	sequencing methods. The bioinformatics sessions provided a practical overview of data analysis tools used in genomic research, covering topics such as sequence alignment, database searches, and genetic variation interpretation. Participants engaged in live demonstrations, hands-on lab sessions, and interactive virtual discussions.
32	Basic molecular biology and bioinformatics analysis	West Africa	Genetics, Genomics, and Bioinformatics Department, National Biotechnology Research and Development Agency (NBRDA), Nigeria	Molecular biology handling of DNA	The workshop aimed to equip participants with both theoretical knowledge and practical skills in essential molecular biology techniques. The theoretical sessions established a foundation in laboratory safety, core molecular biology concepts, and the principles and setup of the PCR. Subsequently, participants engaged in extensive hands-on practical sessions, which includes extracting DNA from both plant and microbial samples, quantifying and visualizing nucleic acids, performing PCR amplifications, and analyzing amplicons via gel electrophoresis. A dedicated bioinformatics module provided hands-on experience in navigating the NCBI databases and performing BLAST analyses. The workshop concluded with a wrap-up session, during which participants presented their current research, articulating how the newly acquired skills would enhance their work.
33	Basic molecular biology	West Africa	University of Calabar, Nigeria	Basic molecular biology	The workshop provided comprehensive hands-on training in essential molecular biology techniques. Participants learned how to extract DNA and RNA from both plant and animal tissues, followed by cDNA synthesis for downstream applications. The sessions also covered PCR and RT-qPCR, enabling participants to quantify gene expression accurately. In addition, trainees practiced agarose gel electrophoresis for nucleic acid analysis and

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					gained experience in interpreting RT-qPCR data. The workshop concluded with a module on primer design, equipping participants with the skills needed to plan and execute robust molecular experiments.
34	Basic molecular biology	Southern Africa	CenGen Training Laboratory, South Africa	Extraction of High Molecular Weight plant DNA for long-read sequencing	This workshop provided participants with the opportunity to acquire practical skills to extract High Molecular Weight (HMW) DNA from challenging plants such as succulents. HMW DNA demands extraction protocol adjustments due to the requirement of long, intact DNA strands of high quality. Inhouse-developed strategies for overcoming inherent plant tissue properties that inhibit DNA quality, such as the presence of polysaccharides, phenolic compounds, latex and mucilaginous tissue, were discussed and applied. Participants used Quiver tree (<i>Aloidendron dichotomum</i>) leaf tissue as experimental starting material. Post-extraction quality control steps and downstream applications for using specifically HMW DNA were also discussed.
35	Basic molecular biology and bioinformatics analysis	West Africa	Institut National d'Hygiène University of Lome, Togo	Basic molecular biology techniques and bioinformatics	Day 1 covered a lecture introducing the quality management system, emphasizing the 12 fundamental elements of QMS, PCR techniques presentation and its applications (qPCR, multiplex PCR, etc.). Manual extraction by the QIAamp Viral RNA Mini kit method presents a strategy of extraction of viral RNA based on the silica membrane. Day 2 focused on automatic DNA/RNA extraction via KingFisher Flex instrument (711-8G1994) using the MagMax Kit (A42352), analysis of multiplex PCR, implementation of positive/negative controls, and qualitative and quantitative detection. Day 3 focused on Interpretation of Ct thresholds, visualization by electrophoresis, introduction to post-PCR bioinformatics

S/N	Practical session thematic area	AfricaBP regional workshop	Name of practical host organisation and country of affiliation	Title of hands-on practical session held	Summary of course content
					analysis. Learning outcomes include, amongst others, mastery of DNA/RNA extraction protocols, good practice in PCR and bioinformatics interpretation as well as ownership of normative and biosafety requirements.
36	Basic molecular biology, biostatistics, and ecology	North Africa	Applied Genetics in Agriculture, Ecology and Public Health Laboratory (GenApAgiE), University of Tlemcen, Algeria	Small ruminant morphometry (sheep and goats) and DNA extraction	This practical aimed to introduce participants to methods for identifying populations using morphological descriptors, which represent the first step in the characterization of genetic resources and the training presents a standardized method for extracting DNA from sheep blood in order to obtain high-quality DNA usable for molecular analyses such as PCR, genotyping, or sequencing. It also covers the essential concepts of biostatistics and the use of R and RStudio to analyze biological data. It began with types of variables, measures of central tendency (mean, median) and dispersion (variance, standard deviation), as well as the main statistical plots. It then introduces RStudio, data import, and normality tests, followed by descriptive statistics: Principle Component Analysis for quantitative data and Multiple Correspondence Analysis for qualitative data, allowing visualization of relationships between variables, interpretation of individuals, handling of missing values, and automatic generation of graphs and reports. Hierarchical Clustering on Principle Components was also presented to group individuals into clusters after a factorial analysis. Finally, it addresses ecological indices such as Shannon and Pielou diversity indices (Kumar et al., 2022; Rosa et al., 2025), the Mahalanobis distance for detecting outlier individuals (Olvera Astivia, 2024), and different types of ANOVA (one-way, factorial, MANOVA) to test

S/N	Practical session thematic area	AfricaBP regional workshop	Name of practical host organisation and country of affiliation	Title of hands-on practical session held	Summary of course content
					differences between groups.
37	Geometric morphometrics and basic moléculaire biology	North Africa	Applied Genetic in Agriculture, Ecology and Public Health Laboratory (GenApAgiE), University of Abou Bekr Belkaid Tlemcen, Algeria	Morphometric analysis using MorphoJ and DNA extraction of insects (case study: <i>Aphis fabae</i>)	This workshop introduces participants to both geometric morphometric techniques and basic molecular methods for studying insect variation, using the black bean aphid (<i>Aphis fabae</i>) as a model organism. The first part focuses on morphometric analysis, where participants learn how to collect anatomical landmarks from insect images, process these data in MorphoJ, and perform shape analyses such as Procrustes superimposition, principal component analysis (PCA), and group comparison. These methods allow users to quantify and visualize morphological differences within and between aphid populations. The second part of the workshop covers DNA extraction procedures, guiding participants through practical steps such as sample preparation, tissue lysis, purification, and DNA quality assessment. Participants gain hands-on experience with extracting genomic DNA suitable for downstream molecular applications (e.g., PCR, sequencing).
38	Morphometric, photogrammetry and 3D	North Africa	Applied hydrology and environment laboratory, Faculty of sciences and technology, University of Ain Temouchent, Algeria	Plant photogrammetry	This workshop was designed to provide participants with a comprehensive introduction to the principles and applications of photogrammetry, with a specific focus on vegetation analysis. Over three days, the program blends theoretical foundations with hands-on practical experience, guiding attendees from the fundamentals of photogrammetry and its environmental applications to the detailed processes of 3D modeling and morphometric analysis of plant leaves. Key objectives include learning to quantify 3D morphological traits, build and analyze 2D and 3D models of leaf structures, introduction to software (e.g., ZEPHYR 3D, ImageJ) and setups

S/N	Practical session thematic area	AfricaBP regional workshop	Name of practical host organisation and country of affiliation	Title of hands-on practical session held	Summary of course content
					applicable to biodiversity and climate impact studies. The agenda progresses from introductory concepts and software setup on Day 1, to practical image acquisition and 2D model building on Day 2, culminating in advanced data processing, volume estimation, and comparative statistical analysis on Day 3, concluding with a feedback session to solidify the learning outcomes.
39	Sampling collections, molecular biology and bioinformatics	West Africa	A.P. Leventis Ornithological Research Institute (APLORI) Molecular Ecology Laboratory, Nigeria	Hands-on training on basic molecular Biology techniques and bioinformatics	This practical workshop was aimed at equipping researchers without prior molecular lab experience hands-on training. It included both theoretical and hands-on components beginning all the way from sample collection to data analysis. Participants engaged in a field session to collect blood samples from birds and learnt the various concepts of sample preservation and handling. In the lab, each participant had hands-on experience with DNA extraction using a manual DNA extraction system (Zymo DNA Mini-Prep) and performed quality control using fluorometric quantification. The session also included a theoretical exploration of other extraction methods for the different nucleic acids. PCR targeting the mtDNA region was carried out following a session on primer design and principles of PCR. The amplicons were visualised on an agarose gel. Parti(Hall, 1999)re introduced to various data analysis tools for working with Sanger sequence data output including MEGA (Kumar et al., 1994), BioEdit (Hall, 1999), Expassy translate tool (Artimo et al., 2012), CAP3 (Huang & Madan, 1999) and EMBOSS (Rice et al., 2000) Merger, and conducted multiple sequence alignment and phylogenetic analysis.
40	Sample	Southern	South African	The Science of	This three-day workshop introduced best practices used for the collection

S/N	Practical session thematic area	AfricaBP regional workshop	Name of practical host organisation and country of affiliation	Title of hands-on practical session held	Summary of course content
	collection and biobanking	Africa	National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI), South Africa	sample collection: Best practices for collecting reliable wildlife and plant samples for research	of both fauna and flora samples for research. Participants were introduced to the value of biobanks and how they contribute to research; ethics, permits and other considerations when making use of biodiversity samples; minimum data standards when collecting biodiversity samples; and a snapshot of the BOLD database (Ratnasingham & Hebert, 2007). An overview of the Biodiversity Biobank South Africa (BBSA) project (Makoni, 2023) was presented to showcase the network of well-managed biodiversity collections in South Africa today, and how these diverse sample types contribute to research. Sampling methodologies, including chain of custody approaches for wildlife and plant collections, efficacy of eDNA sampling, sampling for genetic analysis, forensic sampling, and a hands-on session for the collection of plants for both DNA and herbarium collections were all part of the comprehensive curriculum at the workshop.

African Plant Genome Assembly and Annotation Fellowship

International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) in collaboration with the Inqaba Biotech West Africa and the African BioGenome Project organized a training fellowship on plant genome annotation and assembly (see Hayah, et al (Hayah et al., 2025) for the launch) from 2nd - 6th June, 2025. The hands-on workshop brought together eight (8) participants from five (5) African countries: Nigeria, Ethiopia, Cameroon, Cote d'Ivoire, and Benin Republic. The five-day workshop, hosted at IITA Biosciences (IITA Headquarters, Ibadan) and utilizing the IITA bioinformatics infrastructure, provided researchers with hands-on training in advanced genome assembly and functional annotation of Next-Generation Sequencing (NGS) data, using an endemic African plant genome as a case study. A special focus was on building capacity in *de-novo* genome assembly, quality assessment, scaffolding, and annotation. It focused on blending theoretical knowledge with practical, command-line proficiency. It also addressed a critical gap in African agricultural genomics: underrepresentation of useful African endemic plants in global genomic databases. By providing hands-on training in state-of-the-art assembly and annotation tools, participants were empowered to lead future research on plants, including identifying genes linked to nutrition, disease resistance, and climate adaptability. Additionally, the focus on individual and institutional collaboration aligned with the African Union Agenda 2063's goals of strengthening African-led innovation and food security. The workshop also built computational capacity, as participants gained skills transferable to other crop species, supporting broader efforts to advance genomic research and data-driven biological discovery across Africa. Materials for the training fellowship are available on GitHub in Landi, 2025 (Landi et al., 2025).

Text Box 1

Methodology for One Health analysis

Scoping-level hypothesis: This analysis was designed to examine (and build insights) on how non-biological biodiversity genome metadata may inform One Health processes and stakeholder information as well as how these are integrated within national One Health strategies. The analysis aimed at identifying areas of alignment, divergence, and opportunities, while integrating biodiversity-informed data across sectors. To date the One Health approach in Kenya has focused mainly on the support of human health and health systems in general. Following this, our hypothesis was to demonstrate the importance of One Health approach in Kenya extending beyond disease surveillance and prevention and control of diseases, providing scoping insights into potential integrated One Health approach and how this may potentially enable effective evidence-based decision making across conservation, disease surveillance, antimicrobial resistance management, and food security.

Data gathering: A list of 152 Kenyan species with high national importance in biodiversity, conservation, health, economic development and human livelihood were selected with potential for impacts on conservation, biodiversity management, human health, and public health. These species represent eukaryotic and non-eukaryotic species involving wild plants, wildlife, livestock, birds, insects, fungi, pathogens, reptiles, fishes, arachnids, mammals, and food crops with the following endemism, IUCN status, and ecological role criteria: 1) Endemic status - introduced, native or endemic to Kenya, 2) Ecological role such as predator, producer, consumer, vector, pathogen, 3) International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) status such as least concern, near threatened, extinct, or vulnerable.

Data curation: Data curation was carried out by interrogating Genome on a Tree (GoaT) (Challis et al., 2023), European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) (O’Cathail et al., 2025), International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) red list (<https://www.iucnredlist.org> as of December 2025), Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) (<https://www.fao.org/dad-is/browse-by-country-and-species/en/> as of December 2025) platforms as well as online searches (see example_data/input directory in GitHub repo below). GoaT and ENA were used to respectively determine if eukaryotic and non-eukaryotic species (e.g. viruses and bacteria) have sequenced. Sixty-eight (68) of the species have been sequenced while eighty-four (84) are currently unsequenced. GoaT and ENA were used to determine if the genome of a selected species has been sequenced or not (codified by `goat_taxon_id` and `genome_id` column headers in the input file), the IUCN (for conservation species) and FAO (for livestock and crop species) platforms were used to identify IUCN status (`iucn_status` column header), while online

searches were used to verify species names, custom taxonomic group, ecological role, endemic status, and example location where the species is found. GoaT was used to further determine the assembly level of the species denoted by genome_assembly_level column in the input file.

Data analysis: The scoping-level One Health analysis was executed through a command-line interface using a pipeline implemented in Python v3.10 to support reproducibility, scalability, and integration into automated workflows. Arguments were parsed using a class-based wrapper built on the *argparse* library, for standardized input handling and structured parameter access across the analysis. Input datasets, including genome metadata, One Health process definitions, and stakeholder sector mappings were supplied as comma-separated values (CSV) files and used to generate weighted edge and impact matrices. The genome metadata categories were based on biodiversity-informed One Health analyses per stakeholder across Kenya. Package dependency management was implemented through a Poetry configuration file (*pyproject.toml*), and execution progress was monitored using standard Python v3.10 logging framework. The relationships between species versus stakeholders versus processes (multi-layer One Health network), sectors versus species (clustering heatmap), processes versus stakeholders (sankey plot) and within genomes metadata were also carried out. Heatmaps assess associations between species and the source One Health sectors under consideration. Species were annotated using genome-derived biodiversity metadata, while stakeholder sectors represented institutional components of One Health frameworks. Hierarchical clustering identified patterns of co-occurrence and sectoral alignment while Chi-square was used to determine associations between categorical variables. The pipeline, called *gene2onehealth* (Ebenezer, 2025) and developed as part of the scoping exercise in this paper, is available on GitHub: <https://github.com/ThankGodE/gene2onehealth>

Text Box 2

Lessons learned

The AfricaBP Open Institute regional workshops 2025 increased awareness on biodiversity genomics with an estimated 75% participants being non-AfricaBP members (Figure S4e). Over 88% reported their knowledge of biodiversity genomics improved by at least 40% (Figure S5). In addition to this, the sentiment analysis of 3,476 responses revealed an interest in learning more about bioinformatics tools, sequencing techniques and workflow management (Figure S4). By the end of the workshops including the sessions which covered the areas of interest above, high satisfaction (90% and 50% satisfaction for the awareness and practical sessions respectively) was recorded (Figure S5). Both symposium and practicals were well organised with at least 22% of participants having a good symposium experience and 56% expressed satisfaction with the practical sessions (Figure S5).

Despite the positive feedback, there were few areas participants pointed out for improvement. Better engagement of online attendees beyond an audience based role and increment of time allocated for questions and discussions were significant suggestions raised. This would allow more interactions, learning and significant knowledge sharing. They also hoped for inclusion of segments to spotlight the latest innovations built on the continent. This can boost knowledge sharing and draw sponsors and funding. The need to remove language barriers and ensure better inclusion was also highlighted. At the North African Regional Workshop where some talks were given in french language, certain participants reported the need for translations in the future to ensure comprehension. Interpreters and standardizing the number of languages used at symposiums can help bridge the gap.

Overall, the experience was positive for participants as nearly 84.2% felt the workshop met their expectations and considered its duration appropriate (Figure S5). Sentiment analysis of lecture and practical session feedback identified key themes including “Enough details,” and “Everything is satisfactory” (Figure S5). The general sentiment analysis indicated positive feedback, satisfaction with the workshop, and appreciation for AfricaBP, while suggesting the need for more practical exercises (Figure S5).

Conclusions, recommendations, and forward look

Although NOHSPs are emerging across Africa, fully integrated frameworks across human, animal, plants, and ecosystems, are still not the norm. South Africa and Morocco, albeit their advanced public health and genomics capacities, remain without strategies that comprehensively unify human, animal, plant, and environmental health (see Table 1 and section on landscape of NOHSPs across Africa). This fragmentation in One Health policies compromises disease surveillance, slows responses to outbreaks, and thereby permits preventable health and economic shocks to ripple across sectors. The South African One Health Economics mini-congress stressed the urgent need for a single, coordinated national strategy grounded in shared governance and rigorous economic evidence (Mamabolo et al., 2025). Without such integration, institutional progress risks being symbolic rather than substantive, leaving systems inherently vulnerable to accelerating zoonotic and environmental threats.

AfricaBP advocates for a continent-wide institutionalized NOHSPs that integrates biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics, which are less explicitly captured in current plans. To advance operationalization and sustainability of One Health systems across Africa, AfricaBP sets forth the following actionable recommendations:

- *Sustainable financing:* National One Health frameworks and finances should be integrated into national budget lines to limit dependence on external donor support and ensure long-term stability upon implementation. Africa needs to establish more local NOHSP's and OHNs funded and governed through national and local funding mechanisms to focus on achieving national and regional priorities. The AfricaBP Open Institute regional workshops provide an avenue for such OHNs to be established for biodiversity interests through a bottom up, grassroots approach.
- *Full integration of the three domains of One Health:* National One Health frameworks should move beyond disease-specific responses by embedding continuous environmental, ecological, and animal health to enhance early detection of zoonotic diseases. Similar to the Generalizable One Health Framework (GOHF) in zoonotic disease programmes (Ghai et al., 2022), we recommend to establish an integrated Pan-African One Health Framework for Biodiversity Genomics and Bioinformatics to drive sustainable conservation and food security and better connect socio-economics and policy issues.
- *Strengthen multisectoral governance:* One Health coordination structures should be formalized within government structures, including clear inter-ministerial agreements and defined roles are essential to accelerate implementation of integrated human, animal, and environmental health initiatives. For example, the

National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs) is the main mechanism by which countries develop plans or programmes for the conservation and sustainable use of biological diversity (Zinngrebe, 2023). We recommend that One Health objectives should be mainstreamed into NBSAPs to bring in focus biodiversity interests in the One Health nexus.

- *Improve digital infrastructure and data sharing:* Developing and implementing interoperable One Health information systems and real-time dashboards will improve coordination among human, veterinary, environmental, and climate sectors. This will then be integrated into standardized reporting tools for efficient multisectoral response.
- *Promote community engagement and cross-border collaboration:* Regional harmonization of policies through African CDC, AU-IBAR, is critical for managing shared zoonotic risks.
- Establish unified, comprehensive National One Health Strategic Plans (NOHSPs) across the continent.

AfricaBP plans to integrate genomic and bioinformatics data into national and continental biodiversity programmes and strategies to inform policy decision-making. AfricaBP will do this through its strategic roadmap by providing the necessary quantitative and qualitative data on the impact of biodiversity to One Health at both biological and non-biological depths. We call this data analysis exercise the *Gene2OneHealth* Initiative. The first stage (Phase I, GenomeTaxa2OneHealth) will focus on genome-level coverage contributions (without biological depth) across over a dozen African countries while the second stage (Phase II, GenomeTaxaFunctions2OneHealth) will focus on gene-levels contributions (with biological depth) mapped to genomes, taxa and interactions with relevant African stakeholders, countries, and One Health elements. In 2026, AfricaBP will establish the *African Congress on Digital Sequence Information, Infrastructural Development and Policy* to power African DSI infrastructures through deeper policy discourse, including organising several workshops on how artificial intelligence can be leveraged to accelerate biodiversity monitoring, species identification, ecological modeling, and conservation planning through the integration of data such as genomics, bioinformatics, spatial and environmental.

Acknowledgements

This work has benefited from the support and resources provided by the African BioGenome Project (AfricaBP). We would like to thank all keynote, guest, oral and poster presenters at the West, East and Central, Southern and North Africa regional workshops 2025 as well as all partners, sponsors, participants, and other contributors, for their contributions during the symposium sessions of the regional workshops. For a comprehensive list of acknowledgements please see (African BioGenome Project, 2025a): <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/K564P>

Competing interests

- F. Smit, E. Wessels, and M. White are employees of Cengen (Pty) Ltd.
- L. K. Mbabu and E. Kiragu are employees of Change Biotec Limited
- C. R. Waruhiu, E. Ager, S. Gicharu, B. Machua, P. N. Mwangi, and D. Obute are employees of F&S Scientific
- L. Fardeheb, S. Kahia Tani, A. Kermouni Serradj, and C. Lokesh are employees of Genethical
- B. Andika, D. M. Kivuva, W. Nyakundi, and V. W. Wambua are employees of Inqaba Biotec East Africa Ltd.
- A. O. Adediji, E. R. Kwasi, and A. E. Olumeh are employees of Inqaba Biotec West Africa
- N. Shabangu and B. Wurdeman are employees of MGI-Tech
- O. Elekima, S. L. Gillis-Harry, J. E. Ideozu, and F. U. Igwe are employees of MyAfroDNA
- N. Kitchin and J. Potgieter are employees of Separations
- B. Gesimba is an employee of Shomoro technologies
- C. Bezuidenhout is an employee of The Africa Genomics Center and Consultancy

Author contributions

S/N	Author name	Literature review	Design and generation of manuscript diagrams	Survey development and collection	Survey analysis	Developed course content (trainer)	Delivered course content (trainer)	Secured grant that executed practical workshop	Organised and coordinated regional workshop	Hosted a practical workshop	Practical workshop instructor	Fellowship coordination	Fellowship reviews and assessments	Manuscript drafting	Manuscript revision	Supervision - oversight and leadership responsibility	Correspondence with Journal	Manuscript review
1	Jacinta Abalaka					✓	✓			✓	✓							✓
2	Asmaa Abushady							✓		✓								✓
3	Victoria Adedeji					✓	✓				✓							✓
4	Adedapo Adediji					✓	✓			✓	✓							✓
5	Andrews Frimpong Adu					✓	✓	✓		✓	✓							✓
6	Elvince Ager					✓	✓				✓							✓
7	Shakirat Ajenifujah-Solebo					✓	✓	✓		✓	✓				✓			✓
8	Genereux Akotenou						✓				✓							✓
9	Belei Wemboo Afiwa Halatoko					✓				✓								✓
10	Nabil Amor					✓	✓	✓		✓	✓							✓
11	Brian Andika					✓	✓				✓							✓
12	Bouabid Badaoui					✓	✓		✓	✓								✓

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13	Mai Barakat					✓	✓			✓	✓			✓		✓		✓
14	Komlan Batawila								✓	✓								✓
15	Zewdu Edea Bedada						✓	✓	✓									✓
16	Fatima Zahra Belharfi						✓											✓
17	Solomon Beyene					✓	✓			✓	✓							✓
18	Carlos Bezuidenhout							✓										✓
19	Johannes Bezuidenhout					✓	✓											✓
20	Kaoutar Bourak									✓	✓							✓
21	Ezra Byakora									✓								✓
22	Nadia Carstens									✓								✓
23	Narjice Chafai					✓	✓		✓		✓							✓
24	Kimberly Coetzer					✓	✓				✓							✓
25	Hewan Demissie Degu					✓	✓			✓	✓			✓	✓			✓

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26	Rim Drouzi					✓	✓				✓							✓
27	ThankGod Echezona Ebenezer	✓	✓	✓					✓			✓	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓
28	Achraf El Allali					✓	✓	✓		✓								✓
29	Owanate Elekima					✓	✓				✓							✓
30	Assem Elsherif					✓	✓		✓		✓							✓
31	Ojochenemi Aladi Enejoh					✓	✓				✓							✓
32	Victor Ezebuio					✓	✓	✓		✓	✓							✓
33	Nidal Fahsi									✓	✓							✓
34	Linda Fardeheb					✓	✓											✓
35	Sarra Farjallah					✓	✓	✓		✓	✓							✓
36	Nabil Fikraoui									✓	✓							✓
37	Semir Bechir Suheil Gaouar					✓	✓	✓		✓								✓
38	Yohannes Gedamu Gebre					✓	✓			✓	✓							✓

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39	Owunari Georgewill							✓										✓
40	Barrington Gesimba						✓			✓								✓
41	Samira Ghoor							✓		✓				✓				✓
42	Emna Ghouili					✓	✓											✓
43	Samuel Gicharu									✓								✓
44	Andreas Gisel					✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓						✓
45	Jesse Gitaka							✓		✓								✓
46	Fatma Guerfali									✓								✓
47	Roba Hamed Mostafa					✓					✓							✓
48	Sotonye Leslie Gillis-Harry					✓	✓			✓	✓							✓
49	Asmaa Hassan						✓				✓							✓
50	Sameh Hassanein					✓	✓				✓							✓
51	Ichrak Hayah					✓		✓						✓				✓
52	Mohamed Hijri									✓								✓

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53	Justin Ideozu					✓	✓	✓		✓								✓
54	Franca Umasoye Igwe					✓				✓								✓
55	Dahaoui Ikram Ines							✓										✓
56	Faiza Ilias					✓	✓	✓		✓								✓
57	Hakim Kaddour					✓	✓	✓		✓								✓
58	Samuel Paul Kagame								✓					✓				✓
59	Samira Kahia Tani					✓	✓	✓		✓								✓
60	Agneton Kakungu									✓								✓
61	Jonathan Kalami						✓				✓							✓
62	Bernard N. Kanoi									✓					✓			✓
63	Lewis Karani					✓	✓			✓	✓							✓
64	Sally Mueni Katee					✓	✓			✓								✓
65	Bekkar Kawther							✓										✓
66	Fredrick Kebaso					✓	✓			✓								✓

S/N	Author name	Literature review	Design and generation of manuscript diagrams	Survey development and collection	Survey analysis	Developed course content (trainer)	Delivered course content (trainer)	Secured grant that executed practical workshop	Organised and coordinated regional workshop	Hosted a practical workshop	Practical workshop instructor	Fellowship coordination	Fellowship reviews and assessments	Manuscript drafting	Manuscript revision	Supervision - oversight and leadership responsibility	Correspondence with Journal	Manuscript review
67	Ahmed Marwane Kermouni Serradj	✓				✓	✓	✓			✓			✓				✓
68	Rana Khalel					✓					✓							✓
69	Anubhab Khan					✓	✓	✓	✓		✓							✓
70	Racheal Kimani								✓	✓								✓
71	Craig Kinnear								✓	✓				✓				✓
72	Esther Kiragu					✓	✓		✓	✓								✓
73	Natasha Kitchin					✓	✓			✓	✓							✓
74	Dennis Kivuva								✓									✓
75	Komi Komi Koukoura						✓		✓	✓	✓							✓
76	Josiah O. Kuja	✓							✓					✓				✓
77	Elejo Roseline Kwasi									✓		✓						✓
78	Kim Labuschagne					✓	✓	✓		✓								✓
79	Michael Landi					✓	✓				✓							✓
80	Anja le Grange						✓			✓	✓							✓

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81	Niguse Kelile Lema					✓	✓				✓							✓
82	Chidananda Lokesh					✓	✓											✓
83	Wenceslaus C. Madu								✓	✓								✓
84	Brian Machua					✓	✓				✓							✓
85	Antoine Mafwila					✓	✓			✓	✓							✓
86	Issaka Maman							✓		✓								✓
87	Mudzuli Mavhunga					✓	✓				✓							✓
88	Christina Meiring					✓	✓		✓	✓	✓							✓
89	George N. Michuki					✓	✓			✓	✓							✓
90	Tabet Aoul Mohamed Wassim							✓										✓
91	Benhamadi Mohammed El Amine							✓										✓
92	Prudent Mokgokong					✓	✓	✓		✓	✓							✓

S/N	Author name	Literature review	Design and generation of manuscript diagrams	Survey development and collection	Survey analysis	Developed course content (trainer)	Delivered course content (trainer)	Secured grant that executed practical workshop	Organised and coordinated regional workshop	Hosted a practical workshop	Practical workshop instructor	Fellowship coordination	Fellowship reviews and assessments	Manuscript drafting	Manuscript revision	Supervision - oversight and leadership responsibility	Correspondence with Journal	Manuscript review
93	Morad M. Mokhtar					✓	✓				✓							✓
94	Ismail Mouhrach									✓	✓							✓
95	Ahmed Moustafa					✓	✓			✓						✓		✓
96	Benard Mugisha					✓	✓			✓	✓							✓
97	Anne WT Muigai	✓						✓						✓	✓			✓
98	Zahra Mungloo-Dilmohamud												✓	✓				✓
99	Shane Murray						✓											✓
100	Sadik Muzemil						✓						✓	✓	✓			✓
101	Monica Mwale					✓	✓											✓
102	Peter Nthiga Mwangi									✓	✓							✓
103	Martin Naicker					✓	✓											✓
104	Olivier Nicky					✓	✓				✓							✓
105	Helen Nigussie					✓	✓	✓	✓					✓				✓
106	Valentine Otang					✓	✓			✓	✓				✓			✓

S/N	Author name	Literature review	Design and generation of manuscript diagrams	Survey development and collection	Survey analysis	Developed course content (trainer)	Delivered course content (trainer)	Secured grant that executed practical workshop	Organised and coordinated regional workshop	Hosted a practical workshop	Practical workshop instructor	Fellowship coordination	Fellowship reviews and assessments	Manuscript drafting	Manuscript revision	Supervision - oversight and leadership responsibility	Correspondence with Journal	Manuscript review
	Ntui																	
107	William Nyakundi									✓								✓
108	Ebele Obichi							✓		✓								✓
109	David Obute					✓	✓				✓							✓
110	Blessing Odogwu					✓	✓			✓	✓							✓
111	Joel Ogwang					✓	✓			✓	✓							✓
112	Johnpaul Okorochoa						✓											✓
113	Okiemute Okpalefe					✓	✓				✓							✓
114	Monday Iko-Ojo Okpanachi					✓	✓			✓	✓							✓
115	Oluwaseyi Samuel Olanrewaju					✓	✓				✓							✓
116	Adetutu Excellence Olumeh					✓	✓				✓							✓
117	Taiwo Omotoriogun					✓		✓										✓
118	Laurah Nyasita Ondari					✓	✓											✓

S/N	Author name	Literature review	Design and generation of manuscript diagrams	Survey development and collection	Survey analysis	Developed course content (trainer)	Delivered course content (trainer)	Secured grant that executed practical workshop	Organised and coordinated regional workshop	Hosted a practical workshop	Practical workshop instructor	Fellowship coordination	Fellowship reviews and assessments	Manuscript drafting	Manuscript revision	Supervision - oversight and leadership responsibility	Correspondence with Journal	Manuscript review
119	Julian Osuji					✓	✓		✓	✓				✓				✓
120	Genevive Osuji								✓	✓					✓			✓
121	Houcemeddine Othman					✓	✓				✓							✓
122	Amged Ouf					✓	✓				✓							✓
123	Jacktone Oyoo						✓			✓	✓							✓
124	Jacques Potgieter					✓	✓			✓	✓							✓
125	Pritika Ramharack					✓	✓			✓	✓							✓
126	Zineb Rchiad					✓	✓			✓								✓
127	Shaimaa Reda					✓	✓		✓	✓	✓							✓
128	Zahra Salah						✓	✓		✓								✓
129	Samson Pandam					✓	✓	✓		✓	✓							✓
130	Ntji Shabangu					✓	✓				✓							✓
131	Abdoallah Sharaf				✓	✓	✓				✓							✓
132	Iyeopu Siminialayi							✓										✓

S/N	Author name	Literature review	Design and generation of manuscript diagrams	Survey development and collection	Survey analysis	Developed course content (trainer)	Delivered course content (trainer)	Secured grant that executed practical workshop	Organised and coordinated regional workshop	Hosted a practical workshop	Practical workshop instructor	Fellowship coordination	Fellowship reviews and assessments	Manuscript drafting	Manuscript revision	Supervision - oversight and leadership responsibility	Correspondence with Journal	Manuscript review
133	Francois Smit							✓	✓									✓
134	Rae Smith		✓		✓													✓
135	Hiroaki Taniguchi					✓	✓			✓	✓							✓
136	Talatu Tende									✓	✓							✓
137	Kassahun Tesfaye							✓		✓								✓
138	Chigoziem Torty								✓					✓				✓
139	Ogbuagu Udensi	✓							✓					✓				✓
140	Erich van Wyk					✓	✓				✓							✓
141	Sammy Wambua					✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓							✓
142	Victoria Wambua					✓	✓			✓	✓							✓
143	Cecilia Rumberia Waruhiu					✓	✓		✓		✓			✓				✓
144	Elsabet Wessels					✓	✓			✓	✓	✓						✓
145	Michaela-Anne White						✓		✓	✓	✓							✓
146	Bret Wurdeman					✓				✓								✓
147	Firas Zemzem					✓	✓				✓							✓

S/N	Author name	Literature review	Design and generation of manuscript diagrams	Survey development and collection	Survey analysis	Developed course content (trainer)	Delivered course content (trainer)	Secured grant that executed practical workshop	Organised and coordinated regional workshop	Hosted a practical workshop	Practical workshop instructor	Fellowship coordination	Fellowship reviews and assessments	Manuscript drafting	Manuscript revision	Supervision - oversight and leadership responsibility	Correspondence with Journal	Manuscript review
148	Renate Dorothea Zipfel					✓	✓				✓							✓
149	Yedomon Ange Bovys Zoclanclounon												✓					✓

Supplementary information

Figure S1: The AfricaBP Open Institute 2025 regional workshops are organized in a model previously described in Sharah, et al., 2024, using local resources.

Figure S2: AfricaBP Open Institute 2025 regional workshops.

Figure S3: AfricaBP Open Institute 2025 regional workshops reveal overlap of attendance.

Figure S4: The AfricaBP Open Institute 2025 regional workshops built awareness on biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics among participants, reaching an estimated 75% of non-AfricaBP members, based on pre-workshop survey analysis.

Figure S5: AfricaBP Open Institute regional workshops 2025 post-workshop survey indicates high participant satisfaction, with the majority (96.2%) expressing interest in similar future workshops.

Figure S1: The AfricaBP Open Institute 2025 regional workshops are organized in a model previously described in Sharah, et al., 2024, using local resources. A: Hub and spoke model for the delivery of the AfricaBP Open Institute Northern Africa regional workshop 2025. **B:** Hub and spoke model for the delivery of the AfricaBP Open Institute Southern Africa regional workshop 2025. **C:** Hub and spoke model for the delivery of the AfricaBP Open Institute East and Central Africa regional workshop 2025. **D:** Hub and spoke model for the delivery of the AfricaBP Open Institute West Africa regional workshop 2025. The hub includes the coordinating host institutions (highlighted in light grey) while the spoke includes the various practical workshops at different satellite locations (highlighted in light blue) across several African countries (highlighted in light green) and their respective sponsors (highlighted in light brown). The numbers (highlighted in orange) depict the number of persons trained by the practical host institution during the 2025 series of the AfricaBP Open Institute regional workshops.

A

ics and

Figure S2: AfricaBP Open Institute 2025 regional workshops. Map of Africa showing countries of origin of registered participants for each of the AfricaBP Open Institute regional workshops held in 2025. **A:** Diagram showing countries of origin of registered participants during the Southern Africa regional workshop. **B:** Diagram showing countries of origin of registered participants during the Eastern and Central Africa regional workshop. **C:** Diagram showing countries of origin of registered participants during the Northern Africa regional workshop. **D:** Diagram showing countries of origin of registered participants during the Western Africa regional workshop (see Sharaf, et al., 2024 for model). This map was generated with AfricaBP registration information using QGIS software v 3.40 (QGIS, 2025), Map data supplied through ArcWorld Supplement.

(A)

(B)

(C)

Figure S3: AfricaBP Open Institute 2025 regional workshops reveal overlap of attendance. UpSetPlots show overlaps between West Africa, East and Central Africa, Southern Africa, and North Africa regional workshops. **A: Registered participants.** West Africa had 1,545 registrants, North Africa 1,379, East and Central Africa 1,114, and Southern Africa 942. Some participants registered for multiple regions, with the largest overlap between East and Central and Southern Africa (188), and 19 participants registered for all four regions. **B: Snapshot headcount of participants.** Attendance records show West Africa 949, North Africa 871, East and Central Africa 806, and Southern Africa 487. Overlaps followed a similar pattern, with 19 participants attending all four workshops. This diagram shows the snapshot headcount during the awareness building session of all the workshops in 2025, and it does not take into account participants who attended the practical sessions but not the symposium sessions. This headcount was conducted using Zoom log in IDs for virtual participants and physical attendance counts. It does not include counts of participants who participated via YouTube and Twitter which has thousands of views across AfricaBP YouTube and Twitter platforms, as at the time of writing this paper. We also had instances where several registered participants preferred to attend the awareness building session of a regional workshop via their university's conference room using a single Zoom ID in which case the headcount is 1, even though there were several participants (see Sharaf, et al., 2024 for details). This Figure was generated by analyzing the Participants ID information with the UpSetPlot Python package (Lex, et al., 2014). **C: Countries of origin of registered participants.** North Africa 56, Southern Africa 50, West Africa 46, and East and Central Africa 46. Thirty-one countries were represented consistently across all four regions. UpSetPlot was generated using custom scripts and libraries: Python and UpSetPlot.

(m) Impact of ethical, social and policy requirement for sample collections have any effect on the scope of your research work (n = 944)

(n) Topics of interest for the participants in getting training during the workshop (n = 3476)

(o) Participants feeling on knowledge gained in this workshop to impact your institution in Africa afterwards (n = 4663)

Figure S4: The AfricaBP Open Institute 2025 regional workshops built awareness on biodiversity genomics and bioinformatics among participants, reaching an estimated 75% of non-AfricaBP members, based on pre-workshop survey analysis. (a-e) General participant demographics, including gender, age, and country of origin. **(f-i)** 85.1% of participants are currently engaged in genome projects, and 52.7% report being very familiar with ethical, social, and policy requirements for sample collection. **(j)** 61% of participants reported limited familiarity with biodiversity resources and repositories for conservation. **(k-l)** Participants have moderate experience with genomic technologies (35.8%), and 84.2% acknowledge the need for genomic databases. **(m)** Sentiment analysis of 944 responses shows a largely positive attitude toward ethical, social, and policy requirements, highlighting respect, research reliability, engagement with local communities, and broader impact; challenges included permits, sample sizes, funding limitations, and regulatory compliance. **(n)** Sentiment analysis of 3,476 responses indicates participants' strong interest in bioinformatics tools, sequencing techniques, and workflow management (e.g., Nextflow). **(p)** Analysis of 4,663 responses reveals positive attitudes toward knowledge transfer, training and mentoring, establishing regional partnerships aligned with AfricaBP, and conducting impactful genomics research addressing Africa-specific health and biodiversity challenges. Statistical and sentiment analyses were conducted using custom scripts and libraries: Python, NLTK for sentiment analysis, and BERTopic for topic modeling, with visualizations in matplotlib and seaborn.

(a) Information given was interesting and easy to understand

(b) Information given is useful to me and my institution in Africa

(c) The right amount of information was presented

(d) There was enough time for discussions, questions and answers

(e) Participants' knowledge of biodiversity genomics or bioinformatics has improved by

(f) Participants' experience on symposium session

(g) Hands-on practical section was very clear and easy to follow

(h) First time involvement of participants in a practical session in Molecular Biology and Genomics

(i) Anything missing in the practical sections

(j) Rate your satisfaction with the practicals

(k) Participants' experience with the practical workshop

(l) Workshop met Participants' expectations

(m) The workshop was of the right length of time

(n) Gender was balanced among the presenters

(o) Workshops to be organized by the AfricaBP in future

(p) Topics missing or issues from the lecture session (n = 154)

(q) Topics missing or issues from the practical session (n = 145)

(r) Topics that was not covered in the workshop participants expected (n = 306)

(s) Participants queries with workshop (n = 89)

(t) Participants feedback on workshop (n = 154)

Figure S5: AfricaBP Open Institute regional workshops 2025 post-workshop survey indicates high participant satisfaction, with the majority (96.2%) expressing interest in similar future workshops. 90% and 50% participant satisfactions for the awareness and practical sessions respectively. **(a-d)** At least 51.5% of respondents strongly agreed that the information presented was engaging, useful, and delivered in the right amount. **(e)** Over 88% reported that their knowledge of biodiversity genomics improved by at least 40%. **(f)** At least 22% reported having a good symposium experience. **(g-i)** Strong agreement ($\geq 57\%$) was observed regarding the ease of the practical sessions. **(j)** 56% expressed satisfaction with the practical sessions, with at least 18.5% rating their experience as good. **(l-m)** Nearly 84.2% felt the workshop met their expectations and considered its duration appropriate. **(n-o)** 96.2% agreed that similar workshops should be organized in the future. **(p-r)** Sentiment analysis of lecture and practical session feedback identified key themes: “Enough details,” “Everything is satisfactory,” “Everything was amazing,” with some requests for more AI-related topics. **(s)** Overall sentiment analysis indicated positive feedback, satisfaction with the workshop, and appreciation for AfricaBP, while suggesting the need for more practical exercises. Statistical and sentiment analyses were conducted using custom scripts and libraries: Python, NLTK for sentiment analysis, and BERTopic for topic modeling, with visualizations in matplotlib and seaborn.

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